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6G Goal-Oriented **AI**-enabled **L**earning and **S**emantic Communication Networks
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Deliverable D5.1

Semantic Network Resource Management
(intermediary specification)

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Editor(s):	Nicola Cordeschi (CNIT)
Authors:	Nicola Cordeschi (CNIT), Lanfranco Zanzi (NEC), Xi Li (NEC), Deniz Gunduz (ICL), Meng Hua (ICL), Tony Q.S. Quek (SUTD), Zihan Chen (SUTD), João Henrique Inacio de Souza (AAU), Xinyi Lin (TOSH), Peizheng Li (TOSH), Adnan Aijaz (TOSH), Olivier Forceville (HPE France), Mattia Merluzzi (CEA), Mateus Pontes Mota (CEA), Francesca Costanzo (CEA), Jary Pomponi (CNIT), Paolo Di Lorenzo (CNIT), Emilio Calvanese Strinati (CEA).
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Abstract

This deliverable presents intermediate results from the 6G-GOALS project focusing on the specification and evaluation of semantic network resource management mechanisms. It introduces novel AI-driven strategies for optimizing spectrum sharing and orchestrating computational resources in Goal-Oriented (GO) and Semantic-Oriented (SO) communication scenarios. Building on previous investigations, this document explores advanced concepts such as Semantic Cognitive Radio (S-CR), goal-effectiveness metrics, Over-the-Air Computing (OAC), and dynamic Deep Neural Network (DNN) splitting with Early Exiting (EE). It provides simulation insights and experimental results demonstrating how semantic and goal-driven paradigms can improve energy efficiency, reduce latency, and enhance spectral efficiency in future 6G networks. Furthermore, it proposes dynamic orchestration techniques that leverage semantic awareness and learning-based adaptation to optimize resource utilization in heterogeneous and resource-constrained environments.

Keywords

6G, Semantic Communication (SemCom), Goal-Oriented (GO) networking, AI-based orchestration, Semantic Cognitive Radio (S-CR), energy efficiency, Over-the-Air Computing (OAC), Deep Neural Network (DNN) splitting, Early Exiting (EE), Knowledge Base (KB).

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	4th Generation
5G	5th Generation
5G-NR	5G New Radio
5QI	5G Quality Indicator
6G	6th Generation
ACK	ACKnowledgement
ADOTA-FL	Adaptive Over-The-Air Federated Learning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AMP	Approximate Message Passing
ARQ	Automatic Repeat Request
BER	Bit Error Rate
BS	Base Station
BSR	Buffer Status Reports
CE	Control Element
CN	Core Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
CR	Cognitive Radio
CS	Compressed Sensing
CSI	Channel State Information
CU	Centralized Unit
DCCH	Dedicated Control Channel
DCT	Discrete Cosine Transform
DL	Downlink
DNN	Deep-learning Neural Network
DO	Data-oriented
DT	Digital Twin
DTCH	Dedicated Traffic Channel
DU	Distributed Unit
EEDNN	Early Exits DNN
EM	Expectation Maximization
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
FEEL	Federated Edge Learning
FL	Federated Learning
FLOP	Floating Point Operations
FSKMV	Frequency Shift Keying-based Majority Vote
GAE	Generalized Advantage Estimation
GEARR	Goal-effective Achievable Rate Region

GNN	Graph Neural Network
GO	Goal-oriented
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
IB	Information Bottleneck
IFed	Ideal Federated Learning
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSCC	Joint Source and Channel Coding
KB	Knowledge Base
KL	Kullback-Leibler
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LCID	Logical Channel Identifier
MAC	Medium Access Control
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MV	Majority Voting
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAC	Over the Air Computing
OAMS	Operation Administration and Maintenance system
OBDA	One-Bit Digital Aggregation
O-RAN	Open RAN
OT	Optimal Transport
OTA	Over-the-Air
PA	Perfect Aggregation
PAPR	Peak-to-Average Power Ratio
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PHR	Power Headroom Report
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization
PRB	Physical Resource Block
PSD	Power Spectral Density
QI	Quality Indicator
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RF	Radio Frequency
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RLC	Radio Link Control
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RRC	Radio Resource Control
S-CR	Semantic Cognitive Radio
SDU	Service Data Unit
SemCom	Semantic Communication
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent

SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise
S-NSSAI	Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SO	Semantic-oriented
S-RIC	Semantic Radio Access Network Intelligent Controllers
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
TDL	Topological Deep Learning
TNN	Topological Neural Network
UDM	Unified Data Management
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UPF	User Plane Function
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
XAR	Extended Reality

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this Deliverable

The primary objective of this deliverable is to investigate, design, and optimize network resource allocation to enable effective semantic-oriented (SO) communications focusing on the exploration and validation of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven techniques that i) enhance energy efficiency, ii) optimize spectrum usage, and iii) improve communication performances while considering heterogeneous resources related to sensing, communication, and computing.

A critical aspect herein is energy and computationally efficient semantic communication, where AI techniques such as Deep Neural Network (DNN) splitting and Reinforcement Learning (RL) are leveraged to balance computational and communication resources across devices and edge servers. These methods enable goal-oriented communication, transmitting only meaningful features to minimize energy consumption while maintaining accuracy and robustness.

Moreover, in this context, the coexistence of goal-oriented (GO) and legacy data-oriented (DO) systems requires innovative spectrum-sharing strategies to optimize wireless resource utilization. Semantic Cognitive Radio (S-CR) extends traditional Cognitive Radio (CR) concepts by integrating AI-driven semantic processing, enhancing spectrum utilization even in the presence of interference from legacy systems.

Another key aspect is related to the Over the Air Computing (OAC), which represents a groundbreaking approach to further improve spectral efficiency by aggregating data directly over the wireless channel, reducing communication overhead and enabling scalable Federated Learning (FL).

1.2 Advancements in This Deliverable

This deliverable presents the results of applying semantic communication mechanisms in real-world scenarios, showcasing the improvements in spectrum efficiency, energy consumption, and latency achieved through AI-driven orchestration. Specifically, it explores:

- *AI-Based Orchestration:* Novel orchestration methods aimed at balancing radio and computing resources through AI-driven techniques, optimizing energy-efficient, low-latency semantic communications.
- *Dynamic Spectrum Management:* Innovative spectrum sharing strategies that leverage the computational capabilities of network nodes, enabling the coexistence of GO and legacy DO users. This section highlights the concept of Goal-Effective Achievable Rate Regions (GEARRs) and the use of S-CR to optimize spectrum utilization.
- *OAC:* Investigation of techniques to enable efficient aggregation of information across multiple devices, reducing communication overhead in FL scenarios while enhancing robustness against signal degradation.
- *Resource Allocation for Semantic-Aware Image Transmission:* Development of reinforcement learning-based optimization systems to dynamically allocate power, bandwidth, and semantic compression models, ensuring high-quality image transmission while minimizing energy consumption and transmission delay.

1.3 Structure of This Document

This document is structured as follows:

Section 2: Spectrum Efficiency and Resource Management in Semantic Networks—This section delves into novel spectrum-sharing strategies that optimize wireless resource utilization for GO and legacy DO systems. Key topics include the coexistence of GO and DO users, S-CR,

and dynamic spectrum management techniques to enhance communication efficiency in semantic networks.

Section 3: AI-Based Orchestration for Energy-Efficient Semantic Communications—This section presents AI-driven approaches for orchestrating energy-efficient semantic communications. It explores methods like DNN splitting and RL to balance computational loads, minimize energy consumption, and ensure timely goal-oriented communication.

Section 4: OAC-Focusing on OAC techniques, this section investigates approaches to aggregate information directly over wireless channels, enhancing spectral efficiency and supporting scalable FL. Topics covered include adaptive FL, massive access-based OAC, and the application of Topological Neural Networks (TNN) in wireless environments.

Section 5: Conclusions—the deliverable concludes the deliverable with future work remarks.

2 Spectrum Sharing in Semantic and Goal-Oriented Networks

Semantic and GO networks are not just data pipelines that transport information based on bit-level fidelity. They are rather intelligent multi-agent systems in which, *i)* communication requirements are flexibly managed with the scope of achieving the goal of accurately transmitting the meaning underlying information, and *ii)* communication and computing play an equally relevant role, opening up new opportunities for wireless resource sharing. In fact, computing power and consequent deployed intelligence can be traded with wireless performance, including transmit power, bandwidth, channel coding, and interference. This section proposes novel spectrum sharing strategies that take into account the actual capabilities of network nodes (e.g., users and access points) to extract relevant information, correctly interpret received information/play a correct action, even in the presence of interfering *classical* nodes that use the spectrum with the legacy objective of accurately transport information in the bit-level sense. The analysis demonstrates that computational power at different nodes and application layers can be leveraged as a trade-off against interference and opportunistic spectrum usage, ultimately impacting physical-layer performance. As an example, motivating these investigations, in Figure 2-1, we show the accuracy of a classification task of four different state-of-the-art models, as a function of the bit error rate (BER). As illustrated, more complex models (i.e., requiring more computational resources) exhibit enhanced robustness to wireless communication noise.

Figure 2-1 Inference performance of four different models under bit-level errors (a) and their associated cost in terms of GFLOPs (b)

This kind of general finding opens new opportunities for a cross-layer interaction that aims at flexibly adapting the quality of communication, based on application needs and computational load (translated in resource and energy costs).

In Section 2.1, we present a spectrum sharing framework that assumes cooperation between GO and DO (legacy) users. Going further, Section 2.2 extends to the non-cooperative opportunistic use of the spectrum, presenting the challenges related to CR settings.

2.1 Coexistence of goal-oriented and legacy system: beyond classical interference constraints

In this first section, a dynamic method for spectrum sharing is proposed, with the goal of accommodating a legacy DO user on the same spectrum resources with a GO user. The general idea is to manage interference in an application and computation-aware fashion, trading off DO user performance, goal achievement metrics, and computational resources in a long-term dynamic fashion.

2.1.1 State of the art: gap analysis and contribution

A few works have already focused on spectrum coexistence between semantic, GO, and DO systems. In [MLG+23], the authors propose a semi-non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) scheme for a two-user downlink communication. They show how semantic communication can improve the performance of a DO communication in terms of achievable rate region. However, the authors focus only on the received semantics, while not considering the actual goal of communication. Also, different computing resource availability regimes are ignored in the paper. A similar approach is proposed in [LC22] for uplink communication, considering different multiple access schemes, to characterize the trade-off between semantic user rate and DO user classical rate. Again, the goal of communication is limited to correctly receiving the meaning, and computing resource aspects are not considered. In [MFG+23], GO communication is introduced in the problem, with a scheme that proposes to learn goal-achieving communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to adapt the level of interference from a DO user to allow a GO user to achieve its goal, in this case confident inference on time. As a limitation, [MF25] considers a single inference model at the edge server, without the possibility to adapt to the quality of received data in case of bad channel conditions.

In this section, the reference scenario is extended to the case in which multiple inference models, with different performance and computational costs, are available at the edge server. The assumption is that they can be dynamically selected to balance computational cost, GO performance, and DO performance.

2.1.2 System model

The system under investigation is illustrated in Figure 2-2.

It is composed of one wireless access point embarked with computing resources and a set of inference models (e.g., AI models), pre-trained and ready to output inference results on data continuously collected by a GO user. At the same time, a DO user uses the same spectrum resources to upload information. The objective of the DO user is to obtain the maximum data rate from the network, without preventing the GO user to achieve its goal, which in this case is defined as retrieving correct inference results within a deadline, with a certain probability. This probability reflects the metric of goal-effectiveness described in [6GGOALS-D21].

2.1.3 Key Performance Indicators

In this section, we exploit both classical and GO KPIs, as detailed in what follows. We use the notation \bar{X} for the long-term average of a generic random variable X .

Figure 2-2 DO and GO users sharing the same spectrum resources

Goal-oriented user inference delay

We consider time as divided into slots t of equal duration τ . Without loss of generality, we assume that the GO user has a new inference request at each slot, with: (a) $N_s(t)$ the number of samples in the batch; (b) $N_b(t)$ the number of bits used to represent each sample. Denoting by W the available bandwidth, and by $M(t) \in \mathcal{M}$ the modulation order belonging to a set \mathcal{M} , assuming an uncoded modulation, the transmission delay of the GO user to transfer a data batch to the edge server is

$$D_{\text{tx}}(t) = \frac{N_b(t)N_s(t)}{\log_2(M(t))}.$$

Then, assuming model $l(t)$ (belonging to the set of inference models \mathcal{L}) is used for inference at time t , we can write the computing delay as

$$D_c(t) = \frac{N_s(t)\omega_{l(t)}}{F(t)},$$

where ω_l denotes the number of floating-point operations (FLOPs) needed to run inference on one sample, and $F(t)$ denotes allocated computing resources (i.e., FLOPS) by the edge server at time t . Then, the overall delay for inference (omitting result transmission, which can be added with minor modifications to the system model) can be written as follows:

$$D_{\text{tot}}(t) = D_{\text{tx}}(t) + D_c(t).$$

Goal-oriented user bit error rate inference reliability and goal-effectiveness

Denoting by $\text{SINR}_g(t)$ the signal-to-interference-plus-noise (SINR) ratio for the GO user, and assuming an uncoded M-QAM modulation, we approximate the BER as follows [Gol05]:

$$P_b(t) = \frac{4}{\log_2 M(t)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{M(t)}}\right) Q\left(\frac{3 \cdot \text{SINR}_g(t)}{M(t) - 1}\right).$$

We assume that each model is described by a tuple $(\omega_l, \Gamma_l(P_b))$, with $\Gamma_l(P_b)$ a reliability metric, e.g., the accuracy for a classification task. Then, merging delay and reliability, we define the goal-effectiveness as [MFG+23]:

$$\bar{\Gamma}_g = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \Gamma_{l(t)}(P_b(t)) \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{D_{\text{tot}}(t) \leq D_{\text{max}}\}} \right\},$$

with $\mathbb{1}\{\cdot\}$ the indicator function and D_{max} a delay threshold set as a requirement. The expectation is taken with respect to random context parameters and optimised resources including transmit power (affecting BER and thus reliability) and model selection (affecting reliability, delay and compute resource utilisation).

DO user data rate and queueing delay

For the DO user, we assume an infinite buffer, fed by new arrivals and drained by transmitting data. From queueing theory, we know that queue strong stability is guaranteed only if the departure rate is greater than the arrival rate. Then, as in [Nee10], [LQ14], [MBC22], we aim to maximize the arrival rate under queue stability, as a way of maximizing the departure rate, i.e., the DO average data rate. As such, we define a buffer for the DO user, which evolves as

$$Q_d(t+1) = \max(0, Q(t) - \tau R_d(t)) + A_d(t),$$

where $A_d(t)$ are the new arrivals at time t , and $R_d(t)$ is the DO data rate (in bits/s) at time t , which we write as follows to consider, respectively, interference- and noise-limited portions of the slot:

$$R_d(t) = \frac{D_t}{\tau} W \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_d(t)) + \frac{(\tau - D_t(t))}{\tau} W \log_2(1 + \text{SNR}_d(t)).$$

The reason is that the GO user only interferes during data upload, while it remains silent for the rest of the slot.

Then, to guarantee queue strong stability, either the DO user increases the average transmit power and thus interference (e.g., forcing the GO user to use more robust but computationally intensive inference model) or it proactively drops arrivals, which technically realises the *control valve* illustrated in Figure 2-2, originally introduced [Nee10] and used in different works to match the arrival rate to the achievable rate of a wireless system.

Finally, as a last KPI, we can define the average DO user queueing delay:

$$\bar{D}_d = \tau \frac{\bar{Q}_d}{\bar{A}_d}.$$

Goal-effective achievable rate regions

The objective of the solution proposed in this section is to achieve the highest data rate for a DO user, without preventing the GO user to achieve its target goal-effectiveness, under computational load constraints. In other words, the objective is to go beyond the classical concept of achievable rate region, typically defined based on the data rate of a set of users in the interference channels, towards *GEARRs* [MF25]. A GEARR is the set of points $(\bar{\Gamma}_g, \bar{A}_d)$ that can be supported by the network, under a set of external constraints (e.g., computational load constraints). The goal of a joint communication-compute system optimisation is to attain the boundaries of the GEARRs while guaranteeing the required constraints. As an example, Figure 2-3 shows these boundaries for a static case, in which the inference model is fixed, and an exhaustive search is performed to select the DO transmit power that maximises the DO user data rate while guaranteeing the goal-effectiveness.

This benchmark solution does not take into account computational load, which is then dictated by the GO user to meet the delay constraints under the selected modulation order. Simulation parameters are reported in Table 2-1, and results are also compared to an orthogonal multiple access (i.e., interference-free channel) in which the minimum bandwidth needed by the GO user to achieve the goal-effectiveness is allocated, while the rest is allocated to the DO user. For this benchmark, the maximum computational load is considered to maximise comparison fairness.

Table 2-1 simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Carrier freq (GHz) /bandwidth (MHz), noise PSD, noise figure (dB), channel model, \mathcal{M} , number of AP antennas	3.5/3.5/10/-174/ 10/256-QAM/8
Channel model	Rician fading channel, with average path loss obtained with path loss exponent 3.5 and reference path loss $\left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi}\right)^2$ at $d_0 = 1$ m. The Rician factor is set to 4
DO/GO/AP user positions (x,y)	[-15, 0]/[0, 0]/[0, 20] m
DO/GO user transmit power	$p_{tx,d} \in [0,0.1]$ W, linearly spaced/0.1 W
Delay constraint (ms)/slot duration (ms)/ arrivals (bits)	20/20/Poisson with parameter 5×10^6
Inference models/dataset	Mobilenetv3, Resnet-101/50, Vit (vit_b_16)/ Imagenette [How19]

As visible from the figure, a more powerful model achieves better DO user performance at the physical layer, thanks to the enhanced robustness to noise and thus enhanced tolerance to interference. Also, the bandwidth sharing mechanisms opens opportunities to more degrees of freedom, allowing GO and DO user to negotiate spectrum usage based on different requirements that involve application (goal-effectiveness) and computational cost. Now, the objective of the optimisation is to achieve the boundaries of the GEARRS and, possibly, do better in some cases.

Figure 2-3 GEARRs with fixed inference model with bandwidth sharing, against bandwidth splitting (orthogonal multiple access)

Achieving the boundaries of the GEARRs: problem formulation and sketch of solution

To achieve the boundaries in the long-term and in a dynamic fashion, we formulate an optimisation problem with the following control variables: i) DO user transmit power ($p_{tx,d}(t)$), ii) the instantaneous arrivals admitted to the queue, iii) a variable $\gamma(t)$ that allows the GO user to drop packets in case of delay constraint violation or its *altruistic* regime, iv) the selected inference

model $l(t)$ and the instantaneous computing resources $F(t)$, in FLOPS. The resulting optimisation problem follows (more details can be found in [MF25]):

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\{\varphi(t)\}_{\forall t}} \overline{A}_d \\ & \text{subject to } (a) \overline{Q}_d < \infty, \quad (b) \overline{\Gamma}_g \geq \overline{\Gamma}_{g,\text{th}}, \quad (c) \overline{F} \leq \overline{F}_{\text{th}} \\ & (d) 0 \leq A_d(t) \leq A_d^{\text{max}}(t), \quad \forall t, \quad (e) p_{\text{tx},d}(t) \in \mathcal{P}, \quad \forall t \\ & (f) \gamma(t) \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall t, \quad (g) \gamma(t) D_{\text{tot}}(t) \leq D_{\text{max}}, \quad \forall t, \\ & (h) l(t) \in \mathcal{L}, \quad \forall t, \quad (i) 0 \leq F(t) \leq F_{\text{max}}, \quad \forall t. \end{aligned}$$

Then, the objective is to maximise data arrival rate under (in the long-term sense) a queue stability constraint (a), a goal-effectiveness constraint and (b) a computational load constraint (c). Other constraints pertain to the feasible sets of the optimisation variables. They have the following meaning: (d) the admitted arrivals to the queue are non-negative and below the actual arrivals at time t ; (e) the DO transmit power belongs to a predefined discrete set \mathcal{P} ; (f) GO user data samples are either dropped or transmitted for inference; (g) if not dropped, data samples are treated within the delay threshold; (h) the selected model belongs to the set of available models; (i) the compute resource load is non negative and below a maximum value.

Despite its complexity, the problem is solved on a per-slot basis after a decoupling based on stochastic Lyapunov optimisation. The technical details are omitted and the interested reader is referred to [MF25]. The benefit of using this optimisation framework lie on the theoretical guarantees of convergence they provide. Namely, a single hyper-parameter is used to balance objective function and queue stability, with the latter always guaranteed around higher values (thus leading to higher queueing delay) when asymptotically approaching the optimal solution. As a drawback, a full system model is needed, differently from purely data-driven solutions as introduced in the next sections. Additionally, the presented solution requires a single orchestrator at the AP, which needs to be aware of the wireless channels of the two users, as well as the queue state of the DO user.

2.1.4 Numerical results

We run simulations for the same setting as for Figure 2-1, with 20 MHz bandwidth, slot duration $\tau = 20$ ms, and computational load threshold set to 500 GFLOPS. Different goal-effectiveness thresholds are set, as visible from Figure 2-4(a), which shows the DO user queueing delay as a function of the DO user data rate, for different goal-effectiveness constraints. The latter is shown in the altruistic and selfish regimes. The former is obtained by including constraint (f), while the latter is obtained by no allowing sample drops by the GO user. We can notice how the former brings additional gains, but only for lower goal-effectiveness constraints. This first result clearly shows the **link between application requirements and physical layer performance**. At the same time, Figure 2-4(b) shows the evolution of the goal-effectiveness as a function of the time index, averaged over the last 2000 slots, to show the capability of the method to meet the desired constraints. The same pertains to the computational load constraint, as visible from Figure 2-4(c).

2.1.5 Conclusions and future directions

In this section, a novel way of sharing the spectrum was proposed, not only based on physical layer parameters, but with a cross-layer perspective that takes into account inference model performance along with their computational cost. We showed how a dynamic selection of the inference model helps improving performance of a DO user that opportunistically uses the spectrum, in terms of achievable rate under goal-effectiveness constraints for the GO user, and a long-term computational load constraint. This is a first step toward an energy and goal-aware

use of the spectrum in semantic and GO networks. Future investigations include the non-cooperative case, in line with the first investigations on semantic and GO cognitive radio.

Figure 2-4 Trade-off between DO user achievable data rate and DO user queuing delay (a), goal-effectiveness evolution (b), and computational load evolution (c).

2.2 Semantic cognitive radio: a semantic representation of the legacy systems

Extending the concept of CR [MM99], this section presents the S-CR, which aims to improve spectrum utilization in semantic and GO communication through opportunistic spectrum access strategies. Initially, it is described how AI methods and principles of semantic and GO communication can be incorporated into CR to build the S-CR foundation. Then, the challenge of technological neutrality is introduced. This preliminary investigation will serve as the basis for the development of S-CR strategies in the following stages of the project.

2.2.1 Semantic cognitive radio

CR emerged to address the problem of radio spectrum underutilization in wireless communications by exploiting idle frequency bands through opportunistic spectrum access strategies. Its benefits extend to both licensed and unlicensed bands. In licensed bands, a CR system identifies and utilizes the spectrum holes left by the legacy systems, enabling their harmonious coexistence [AA24b]. In unlicensed bands, CR facilitates the coexistence of multiple uncoordinated systems, which continuously monitor spectrum availability, accessing frequency bands only when they are idle, and only for the duration necessary to meet the current communication needs [LCZ+20].

Most spectrum access strategies for CR focus on DO systems, with spectral efficiency (e.g., in bit/s/Hz) and interference as the primary constraints. However, these constraints do not fully translate the requirements of semantic and GO communications, meaning the state-of-the-art

CR is suboptimal for such cases. For instance, it has been shown that, in cyber-physical systems, accurate state estimation with CR-based communication depends on reliable communication rather than high data rates [CCC+14]. Therefore, to achieve extreme spectrum efficiency in SO and GO communications through CR, it is essential to advance the characterization of new scenarios and introduce semantic and GO metrics into spectrum access strategies. These scenarios comprise heterogeneous networks in different forms, where SO and GO systems coexist with DO ones, in licensed or unlicensed bands. Along with the new metrics to be introduced, a deep understanding of such scenarios will shape the constraints to build effective S-CR systems. Ultimately, beyond efficient communication by extracting the relevant data, S-CR users will be able to exploit data semantics to develop opportunistic spectrum access strategies with an enhanced understanding of the radio spectrum.

CR transceivers are built upon three basic blocks: 1) spectrum sensing, 2) dynamic spectrum manager, and 3) transmit power controller, as depicted in Figure 2-5. In the following, we describe how these blocks can be augmented by semantic and GO communication principles and AI methods to achieve a S-CR technology.

Figure 2-5 Basic blocks of a CR transceiver and elements to evolve towards S-CR

2.2.2 Spectrum sensing

A CR user employs a *spectrum sensing algorithm* to identify the available frequency bands and estimate the interference levels they are subject to. The simplest strategy is energy-based detection, which compares the received radio frequency energy during a finite time interval with a predefined threshold. Alternative methods include detection based on the second-order statistics or cyclostationarity of modulated signals in the time, frequency, and space domains [ALL+12]. AI-driven solutions further improve spectrum sensing capabilities by leveraging the radio signals' underlying temporal and spectral features [KTH24]. To achieve maximum benefit from AI-driven solutions, it is possible to introduce a shared *Knowledge Base (KB)* for spectrum sensing, with pre-trained AI models and training databases that can be reused and continuously updated by S-CR users.

In a KB for spectrum sensing, the databases could gather spectrum data produced by different radio technologies (e.g., 5G NR, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth), device types (e.g., access points, moving vehicles, and static sensors), and applications (e.g., GO communications, data-intensive streaming, and mission-critical applications), organized by geographical location and time of the day. This would guarantee that the databases contain representative data, with sufficient information to train models that yield accurate spectrum sensing results in diverse scenarios, including the ones not observed previously owing to the models' generalization ability. Being the other

essential element of the KB, the AI models would represent the shared knowledge of the spectrum environment, which could be transferred, used, and updated across S-CR users. For instance, the AI models could be trained to detect spectrum holes from spectrograms by using deep *Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)* [ACH+22]. Alternatively, aiming devices with constrained computation power, part of the models could be trained to identify spectrum usage through automatic modulation classification by using deep *Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)* [GHS22]. By exploiting the various features in the KB datasets and the characteristics of different model architectures, it would be possible to develop models that satisfy the limitations of specific device platforms and address most of the representative scenarios and spectrum sensing objectives.

With an adequate KB, the S-CR would be equipped with rich information for context-aware spectrum sensing, acquiring a deep understanding of the seasonality of spectrum access and the application-dependent traffic patterns. This strategy can be employed to both detect the spectrum holes and learn the behaviour of interfering users transmitting in these frequency bands. Then, after selecting the frequency bands, those learned behaviours could be exploited by the S-CR user to optimize other transmission parameters instead of just the transmit power. Lastly, an effective KB for spectrum sensing would depend on a management strategy to guarantee improvement over time. To this end, a strategy similar to the one proposed in [6GGOALS-D24] could be applied, comprised by four steps: 1) knowledge acquisition (e.g., spectrum data acquisition), 2) representation (e.g., training of AI models for spectrum sensing), 3) updating (e.g., updating AI models locally based on new spectrum data), and 4) distribution (e.g., transferring AI models across devices).

2.2.3 Dynamic spectrum manager and transmit power controller

After identifying the spectrum holes, a CR user selects, among the available ones, the frequency bands to be used for communication and sets the transmit power level. Such decisions must be taken accounting for the target performance desired by the CR user and, most importantly, the impact on the operation of legacy users. For DO users, both constraints are straightforwardly translated to transmit power and interference. That is not the case for SO and GO users, to which effective dynamic spectrum management necessitates the introduction of semantic and GO metrics in the decision process. To exemplify, in the system model introduced in Section 2.1 the GO user performance is measured by the goal-effectiveness, which depends on the BER, delay, and inference reliability. As the BER is only one of three performance components, having high interference levels in a limited number of transmitted slots might not severely degrade the goal-effectiveness. In summary, achieving a reasonable performance depends on ensuring a balance between the goal-effectiveness components, meaning that a degradation in one can be offset by an improvement in others. Cases like this create opportunities for the S-CR users to adopt more flexible spectrum access patterns, which are not feasible when accounting only for the interference generated to the legacy users.

In addition to the ability to select flexible spectrum access patterns, with S-CR, users can go beyond power selection and optimize other transmit parameters to achieve the desired performance levels. For instance, in image transmission, the parameters of a Joint Source and Channel Coding (JSCC) scheme could be tailored to adapt the transmission of the S-CR user according to the tolerable levels for the perception metric (e.g., the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) introduced in [6GGOALS-D21]) and available spectrum resources, under the constraints regarding the operation of legacy users. Accordingly, the S-CR users would be capable of communicating semantic information at low rates when the spectrum is crowded. The parameters that can be optimized extend from those associated with semantic compression at the application level until the physical layer transmission ones, like beamforming configuration and Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) parameters.

2.2.4 Research challenges

As in conventional CR, one of the main goals when developing the S-CR is attaining *technological neutrality*, meaning that a user should be able to deploy an opportunistic spectrum access strategy without cooperating with legacy users or competing S-CR users. Here, cooperation means any proactive exchange of information between users regarding, e.g., spectrum access patterns, communication activity, or performance levels. Technological neutrality is relatively simple to achieve in DO networks, as the performance of legacy and CR users is dictated by interference and transmit power, respectively. However, for semantic and GO networks, this is a major challenge, as spectrum measurements do not explicitly describe the users' performance. For instance, without additional information, a latency requirement cannot be easily identified by observing only transmit power and bandwidth, differently from data rate. The challenge of technological neutrality is especially critical for enabling the operation of S-CR users in licensed bands, as the legacy systems that own the spectrum license are very restrictive in terms of cooperation. Differently, the scenario with multiple S-CR users operating in unlicensed bands allows more versatile strategies, opening room to introduce a minimum level of cooperation. As an example, the S-CR users can embed their intentions and performance information in parameters detectable by spectrum sensing methods. Then, they can adapt their respective spectrum access strategies to enable a harmonious coexistence, consequently attaining extreme spectral efficiency.

2.2.5 Conclusions and future directions

In this section, the concept of S-CR was introduced to improve the spectrum utilization in semantic and GO communication. The expected gains with the introduction into the spectrum sensing and access of AI methods, a radio spectrum Knowledge Base, and semantic and GO metrics were discussed. Furthermore, the technological neutrality was introduced as the main challenge for S-CR, especially for operation in licensed bands. This preliminary investigation forms the basis for the development of S-CR in the following stages of the project, aiming to achieve extreme spectral efficiency in semantic and GO communication. Future research will focus on the dynamic spectrum management, developing opportunistic access strategies for S-CR in different coexistence scenarios.

3 AI-Based Orchestration for Energy and Computation Efficient Semantic Communications

Energy consumption is a critical challenge in next-generation communication networks, particularly in the context of semantic-oriented systems where efficiency must be balanced with performance. Traditional approaches to network resource management often lead to excessive power usage due to redundant data transmissions and suboptimal computing-resource allocation. This section explores AI-driven orchestration strategies designed to optimize energy and computational efficiency across multiple layers of the network. A key aspect of this approach is the integration of both model-based optimization techniques and purely data-driven RL methods to dynamically adjust transmission power, computational load distribution, and semantic encoding schemes based on real-time network conditions and application demands. Furthermore, this section investigates how goal-effectiveness can serve as a guiding principle for resource allocation, ensuring that energy is used efficiently while maintaining the quality of semantic information exchange. The orchestration framework incorporates adaptive mechanisms for dynamic power regulation, multi-layered resource scheduling, and predictive energy modelling, which collectively enhance system sustainability.

3.1 Model-based and purely data-driven distributed approaches enabling energy-efficient low-latency effective communications

In this section, we present two different but complementary approaches to jointly optimise radio and computing resources towards GO effective communication. Both approaches are developed under the umbrella of DNN splitting as a way to share computational load among end and edge devices, with a GO system optimisation that goes beyond communication KPIs towards goal-achieving resource allocation policies. While the first contribution only considers DNN splitting, the second one introduces early exits as an additional way to balance timeliness, resource consumption, and goal-effectiveness. Herein, goal-effectiveness is defined as the probability for a system accomplishing a particular objective, with the latter heavily reliant on the allocated system resources in terms of communication and computation [MFG+23]. The first case study exploits a purely model-based approach to DNN splitting, while the second one a purely data-driven solution, based on a sequential decision making that is performed via RL. The general reference scenario is illustrated in Figure 3-1, with a device and an AP embedded with the same pre-trained inference model. The model can be dynamically split at different points, to transmit intermediate extracted features (semantics), rather than raw data (first case study). Going beyond (second case study), classification can be early stopped to save computation resources, trading it off with inference performance.

Figure 3-1 System scenario for EE-based GO communication.

3.1.1 First case study: Goal-aware DNN splitting at the edge: a model-based approach

Cooperative edge inference can be performed in either a horizontal or a vertical way. For the former, a set of devices collaborate exchanging relevant information to improve performance that are achieved on (possibly incomplete) local data. For the latter, a resource-poor device benefits from deployed edge resources to offload part of the computation. Full local computation comes with the benefit of privacy preservation and no communication overhead. However, the computational load for the device is the maximum overall. Full offloading comes with the benefit of no computational load for the device, but potential data exposure and communication overhead. Partial offloading via DNN splitting is the most promising solution to dynamically and flexibly select the splitting point, based on communication and computation conditions. Also, transmitting intermediate features (embeddings) potentially comes with the benefits of increased robustness to noise (or, bit-level errors). In Figure 3-2, we show the accuracy of a state-of-the-art model (Mobilenetv2 [SHZ+18]), when splitting at different splitting points under a feature error rate of 0.1 and 0.2. As we can notice, properly selecting the splitting point introduces different robustness to noise.

Building on this result, the results presented in Section 2.1 are extended, with an additional layer of robustness obtained via feature (or, semantic) extraction, beyond model selection. The different robustness of different splitting points to physical layer can be exploited to dynamically and flexibly balance local computation cost, wireless communication, accuracy and delay.

State of the art: gap analysis and contribution

Recent works already investigated the benefits and challenges of DNN splitting for edge inference, with trade-offs and techniques surveyed in [MLR22]. [HBW+19] and [MSS20] propose DNN partitioning schemes to minimize delay and user equipment (UE) energy consumption, respectively. In [SMZ21], the authors highlight how GO compression schemes can be seen as a specific case of DNN splitting. In these scenarios, the end device runs an encoder network, while the edge server employs a decoder network. The encoders compress data taking into account the informativeness with respect to the output of a specific inference task. Under a similar framework, [BBD+23] proposes an inference architecture where an architecture is split between a convolutional encoder, used to perform a GO compression, and a convolutional classifier to complete the inference task at the edge server. These works do not address the problem of optimally and dynamically partition the workload. Instead, [LMA+23] proposes a dynamic SP selection strategy that reduces the energy consumption of a UE to perform an edge assisted image classification task with target delay performance. However, it does not consider the performance degradation (e.g., the effects on the accuracy) introduced by the noisy wireless transmission, and its dependency on the SP selection, i.e., goal-effectiveness requirements from a delay and application perspectives. Going beyond this state of the art, we propose a full cross-layer method that considers communication and compute resource orchestration to achieve the goal (correct and timely inference) with the minimum transmission energy consumption, under computation load constraint at the edge device.

Figure 3-2 Accuracy vs. splitting point (Mobilenetv2 on Imagenette [How19]).

System model: Key Performance Indicators, problem formulation, and solution

We consider a device being served by an AP that is equipped with a set of computing resources, similarly as in Section 2.1.2. Differently from Section 2.1, the device and the AP are embedded with the same pre-trained inference model. Then, dynamic splitting is possible, and intermediate features can be transmitted by the device, instead of raw data. We denote by $\mathcal{J} = \{0, \dots, I\}$ the set of available splitting points, with 0 corresponding to raw data and I to the full local compu-

tation case. Then, we denote by ω_i the cumulative computations (in FLOPS) that must be performed locally when transmitting features after a generic SP i . Similarly, we denote by $n_{b,i}$ the number of bits encoding the features at the output of SP i .

Denoting by $M(t)$ the modulation order, by W the bandwidth, by $F_l(t)$ the local computing resources (in CPU cycles/s), by η the number of FLOPs performed per CPU cycle by the device, and by $F_r(t)$ the edge server computing resources allocated at time t (in FLOPs), we can write the total inference delay (assuming splitting point $i(t)$ is selected) as

$$D_{tot}(t) = \frac{\omega_{i(t)}}{F_l(t)\eta_l} + \frac{n_{b,i(t)}}{W \log_2 M(t)} + \frac{\omega_l - \omega_{i(t)}}{F_r(t)}.$$

Also, as in Section 2.1.2, assuming an uncoded modulation, we write the BER as

$$P_b(t) = \frac{4}{\log_2 M(t)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{M(t)}}\right) Q\left(\frac{3 \cdot \text{SNR}(t)}{M(t)-1}\right),$$

with $\text{SNR}(t) = \frac{|h(t)|^2 p_{tx}(t)}{N_0 W}$ being the signal-to-noise-ratio that depends on the selected transmit power and the current wireless channel ($h(t)$) conditions. Whenever a bit is erroneous, the entire feature is assumed to not be received. All unreceived features are zeroed-out. $P_b(t)$ affects the goal-effectiveness. However, the model *reliability* $\Gamma(P_b(t), i(t))$ depends on the selected splitting point. An example of model accuracy is shown in Figure 3-2, as a function of the BER and for different splitting points. Then, we define the goal-effectiveness as

$$\bar{\Gamma} = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \Gamma(P_b(t), i(t)) \cdot \mathbb{1}\{D_{tot}(t) \leq D_{max}\} \right\}.$$

With the expectation taken with respect to random context parameters and control actions that include the aforementioned cross-layer parameters. Also, we write the transmit energy consumption as $E_{tx}(t) = \frac{p_{tx} n_{b,i}(t)}{W \log_2 M(t)}$, and the computation energy consumption as $E_{comp}(t) = \frac{\kappa \omega_{i(t)} F_l^2(t)}{\eta_l}$. Denoting by $E_{tot}(t) = E_{comp}(t) + E_{tx}(t)$. Then, we formulate the following long-term problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\{p_{tx}(t), M(t), i(t), F_l(t)\}_{\forall t}} \overline{E_{tot}} \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \quad \text{(a) } \bar{\Gamma}_g \geq \overline{\Gamma}_{g,th}, \\ & \quad \text{(b) } p_{tx}(t) \in \mathcal{P}, \forall t, \\ & \quad \text{(c) } M(t) \in \mathcal{M}, \forall t, \\ & \quad \text{(d) } i(t) \in \mathcal{I}, \forall t, \\ & \quad \text{(e) } 0 \leq F_l(t) \leq F_{max}, \forall t, \\ & \quad \text{(f) } D_{tot}(t) \leq D_{max}, \forall t. \end{aligned}$$

For the details on the model-based solution of the above problem, the interested reader is referred to [BMB+24].

Numerical results

We consider the simple scenario of one user and one AP, endowed with computing resources. The simulation parameters are reported in Table 3-1. Figure 3-3(a) shows the energy saving against full local computation, as a function of the goal-effectiveness. It can be noticed how the maximum energy savings are obtained for the lowest goal-effectiveness requirements. This is

due to the fact that, even in harsh propagation conditions, the device can transmit raw data, thus avoiding costly local computation. As the goal-effectiveness requirements increase, the energy saving decreases because local computation is promoted to extract (robust-to-bit-errors) semantics, to be able to achieve better performance under bad channel conditions. To validate this “conjecture”, Figure 3-3(b) shows the average depth of local computation, or, the average splitting point selection, as a function of the goal-effectiveness. As expected, higher goal-effectiveness requires more local computation to improve robustness by extracting features (semantics).

Conclusions

In this section we showed how a goal-aware DNN splitting helps improving the trade-off between energy consumption and goal-effectiveness, with both taking into account communication and computation performance. Under worse wireless channel conditions, inference performance improves if intermediate features (semantics) over raw transmission is promoted. The dynamic splitting point selection introduces additional degrees of freedom in striking the best trade-off between communication and computation performance for the edge inference use case [6GGOALS-D21].

Table 3-1 simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Carrier frequency (GHz)/noise PSD (dBm/Hz), noise figure (dB), channel model, \mathcal{M} , number of AP antennas	3.5/10/-174/ 10/ {4,16,64,256}-QAM/1
Channel model	Rayleigh fading channel, with average path loss obtained with path loss exponent 3.5 and reference path loss $\left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi}\right)^2$ at $d_0 = 1$ m
AP/user position (x,y)	[0, 0]/[70, 70] m
user transmit power	$p_{tx,d} \in [0,0.1]$ W, linearly spaced with 20 elements
Delay constraint (ms)	50
Local computation parameters	$F_l \in [0,3]$ GHz, $\eta = 100$ FLOPs/cycle, $\kappa = 3.7 \times 10^{-28}$
Remote computation resources	Random, Gaussian distribution with mean 100 GFLOPs
Inference model	Mobilenetv2: 20 SP (including full offloading and full local computation)
Dataset	Imagenette [How19]

(a)

(b)

Figure 3-3 Average energy saving and local computation depth as a function of goal-effectiveness

3.1.2 Second case study: Goal-aware DNN splitting and early exiting: a data-driven approach

In this section, we further extend the DNN splitting framework to the case of early exiting as an additional opportunity to save computational resources. In fact, using a standard fixed neural network, the computational cost is the same for all the input samples. However, not all samples have the same complexity in terms of computational power needed for extracting meaningful features for the task at hand. Early Exits DNN (EEDNN) are built and trained in such a way to halt computation if a task-related criterion is met, sparing computational resources [TBH16]. This feature provides additional flexibility when combined with the option to send intermediate results to a remote server. Similarly, as in the previous section, the ultimate goal is to identify the optimal (dynamic) split that balances overall latency, communication overhead, and processing requirements, while still meeting minimum performance standards. The availability of multiple selectable early exits helps overcome the limitations of a fixed model architecture, with the added advantage of enabling tasks to be completed directly on the device without requiring transmission to a remote system. To balance and dynamically select which of these features to use, an online optimization that dynamically decide can be implemented.

State of the art: gap analysis and contribution

This online approach, differently from the existing literature methods such as [BJC+23], [JGM23], and [CK+24], allows for decision which jointly takes into consideration communication, computation, and learning aspects of the model. However, most of the early-exits approaches train the exits jointly and evaluate the halting mechanism atomically at each exit, without taking into consideration how the predictions changed from one layer to another. This approach could lead to good results for easy datasets, while it struggles otherwise. Additionally, it creates a discrepancy between the training approach and the halting one, since the latter is not directly integrated into the former, leading to predictions not incorporating a reliable value of uncertainty, a phenomenon known as overconfidence, exacerbating the gap between training and testing phases. In this study, we overcome this limitation by proposing an EEDNN that builds up the prediction of a generic exit by taking into consideration all the previous ones, in a recursive fashion.

Additionally, the study investigates how early exits, enhanced using the aforementioned recursive approach, can be used in an online RL scenario to correctly select the decision in a sequential fashion.

Proposed system model:

In this scenario, the proposed EEDNN architecture is trained and embedded in an end device, as well as in an edge server that can take over computation whenever needed. The architecture is available at inference time for each timestamp (e.g., an image), with enhanced degrees of freedom on 1) where to place workload using EEs, and 2) when possible, where to stop local computation to promote offloading by sending locally computed features, both based on time-varying wireless and compute resource conditions. To achieve such behaviour relevant parameters, including the size of intermediate results and the computational load, as well as relevant KPIs, including the delay and the accuracy, are taken into account during the optimization steps. The proposed method, fully detailed in [PMD+24], is based on a sequential decision making that makes use of a RL approach, whose reward is defined as a waited sum of communication and computation savings, under inference performance constraints whenever exiting the architecture.

Results

The proposed model requires a novel training paradigm, which directly incorporates a halting mechanism, based on a threshold distance between most probable predictions, making the model more reliable during the inference phase due to better estimation of the certainty of each prediction. Figure 3-4 shows that such training approach leads to better results than other EEDNNs.

Moreover, Figure 3-5 shows results obtained when varying the halting threshold in the proposed EE approach. The figure shows the trade-off between communication payload and computation workload savings, for different constraints on the inference margin obtained when exiting. The communication payload saving is defined with respect to the worst case (maximum size across all splitting points), while the computation workload savings are defined with respect to full local computation up to the last layer, i.e., without early exits or offloading. As it can be noted, the best trade-off is obtained for the blue curve, which however achieves the worst inference performance (correct and timely inference as in the previous section). This trade-off gets worse in the benefit of better inference performance (e.g., red curve).

Conclusions

This study has demonstrated how early exit strategies in DNN splitting can optimize the trade-off between computation, communication, and inference performance. By integrating a recursive approach to early exits, the proposed framework enhances prediction reliability while reducing overconfidence issues. Furthermore, the application of reinforcement learning enables dynamic decision-making, adapting to time-varying network and computational conditions. Results confirm that balancing offloading and local computation leads to significant resource savings while maintaining inference accuracy.

Figure 3-4 The gains in terms of computational complexity required to classify a set of images. Our proposal always achieves better results than other approaches for the same complexity

Figure 3-5 Communication-computation-effectiveness trade-off for various halting thresholds

3.1.3 Dynamic Resource Allocation for Semantic-Aware Image Transmission in Multi-User Edge Networks

Efficient and sustainable image transmission is becoming increasingly important in modern communication systems, particularly in scenarios involving multiple users and edge servers. In this section, we aim to optimize image transmission while minimizing energy consumption and resource waste. Traditional transmission approaches often prioritize accuracy at the cost of high energy use and bandwidth consumption, which can lead to excessive carbon footprints and inefficient resource utilization. To address this, we leverage RL to dynamically allocate power and bandwidth while optimizing the selection of semantic encoding and decoding models. These models vary in compression efficiency and energy consumption, allowing the system to adaptively balance quality and sustainability.

From a sustainability perspective, our proposed method promotes energy-efficient computing and intelligent resource management. By reducing redundant data transmission and optimizing power allocation, the system not only improves communication efficiency but also reduces energy waste, contributing to greener and more responsible network operations. This dynamic and adaptive approach to image transmission represents a significant step toward achieving both high-quality service and environmental sustainability in modern edge computing and communication networks.

State of the art: gap analysis and contribution

Although there are several preliminary research investigations on SemCom from an application-level perspective, challenges related to the sustainability of the overall system operation and the latency of the service delivery have not been fully explored yet. Existing works primarily focus on optimizing semantic extraction, reconstruction, and resource allocation for specific tasks, such as image or text transmission, but often overlook the broader implications of energy consumption and computational efficiency in real-world deployments [SYF+23, LGR+23, LDS+23]. As the adoption of AI-based semantic models grows, their energy-intensive nature raises significant concerns about the sustainability of large-scale systems, particularly in resource-constrained environments like edge networks. Additionally, the latency introduced by complex semantic models and wireless transmission can hinder real-time service delivery, which is critical for applications like autonomous driving, healthcare, and virtual reality. To address these gaps, our work aims to bridge the divide between application-level performance

and system-level sustainability by developing a framework that optimizes semantic communication while ensuring energy-efficient and low-latency service delivery.

System Model and Problem Formulation

Figure 3-6 System model of an AI-driven SCM selection and resource allocation task.

As shown in Figure 3-6, we envision a SemCom-powered cellular network comprising an edge server and a set of resource-constrained devices (users) $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, M\}$. In this setup, we assume that the edge server is expected to handle the computationally expensive tasks such as semantic model training, fine-tuning, storage and updating; the semantic encoding and decoding for all transmissions are performed on the devices. Each device holds a variety of semantic compression models (SCMs) $\mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, S\}$, each with different computational demands and compression performances tailored for image transmission. We use matrix $A \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times S}$ to measure the SCM selection. Particularly, $a_{m,s} = 1$ denotes that the s -th SCM is selected by user m , otherwise $a_{m,s} = 0$. Each user can only select one SCM for a specific image transmission task. In addition, the power consumption and inference time of the s -th SCM are given by $p_{m,c}$ and $\tau_{m,c}$, respectively. During the end-to-end SemCom process, the sender first selects an appropriate SCM for encoding, and the process can be represented as

$$I'_s = \mathcal{C}_{\theta_s}(I_s),$$

where θ_s denotes the encoding parameter of the s -th SCM. On the receiver side, the same SCM is used to recover the semantic information from the received bits \widehat{I}'_s and reconstruct the images, which can be interpreted as

$$\widehat{I}_s = \mathcal{D}_{\alpha_s}(\widehat{I}'_s).$$

The encoded source information with extracted semantic content is packed into binary bits for transmission over the wireless channel. Particularly, for the m -th user, the transmission rate can be expressed as

$$r_m = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_{m,s} g_m}{B_m N_0} \right),$$

where $p_{m,s}$, g_m , B_m , and N_0 denote the transmission power, channel gain, allocated bandwidth, and the noise power, respectively. Based on the transmission rate, the transmission latency can be interpreted as

$$\tau_{m,t} = \frac{|I'_s|}{r_m}.$$

To ensure service quality, we introduce a unified image recovery distortion metric based on the cross-entropy loss function, the recovery distortion of the image sent by the m -th user is modeled as

$$D_m = ||I_s - \hat{I}_s||.$$

The optimization objective of the SCM selection and resource allocation problem is to minimize the image recovery distortion for all users. Moreover, we consider the bandwidth constraint, power constraint, and latency constraint. Let B_{max} be the total bandwidth in the considered cellular network. For each user m , the maximum latency is denoted as $\tau_{m,max}$. The optimization problem can be described as

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{A, P_m, B_m} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} D_m \\ \text{s. t. } & p_{m,c} + p_{m,t} \leq P_m, \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ & \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} B_m \leq B_{max} \\ & \tau_{m,c} + \tau_{m,t} \leq \tau_{m,max}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ & \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} a_{m,s} \leq 1, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \\ & \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} a_{m,s} = 1, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}. \end{aligned}$$

In the following, we propose proximal policy optimization (PPO)-based adaptive SCM selection and resource allocation strategy, which is robust to the dynamic environment and user requirements.

PPO-based SCM Selection and Resource Allocation

Step 1: Train SCM Models

In order to realize the dynamic SCM selection and resource allocation, we first train the SCMs so that they can reconstruct images in a good quality, based on the training loss function TL presented in the later sections.

We intend to apply the variational autoencoder (VAE) structure for image reconstruction, where different SCMs are chosen as the encoder, each with a corresponding decoder at the edge server. The sum of Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence loss, structural similarity index measure (SSIM), and mean squared error (MSE) is the objective function for training the VAE, which ensures that the reconstructed image closely matches the original while enforcing the latent variable distribution to approximate a standard normal distribution. Particularly, we denote MSE as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2,$$

where N is the number of pixels in the image; x_i and \hat{x}_i are the pixel values of the original and reconstructed images, respectively. In addition, the KL divergence loss is defined as:

$$KL = -\frac{\beta}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (1 + \log(\sigma_i^2) - \mu_i^2 - \sigma_i^2),$$

where μ_i and $\log(\sigma_i^2)$ are the mean and log-variance of the latent distribution; β is a weighting factor for the KL loss. Furthermore, SSIM can be expressed as

$$SSIM = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_{\hat{x}}+C_1)(2\sigma_{x\hat{x}}+C_2)}{(\mu_x^2\mu_{\hat{x}}^2+C_1)(\sigma_x^2\sigma_{\hat{x}}^2+C_2)},$$

where μ_x and $\mu_{\hat{x}}$ are the mean intensities of x and \hat{x} ; σ_x^2 and $\sigma_{\hat{x}}^2$ are the variances of x and \hat{x} ; $\sigma_{x\hat{x}}$ is the covariance between x and \hat{x} ; C_1 and C_2 are constants to stabilize the division. The total loss is subsequently modelled as

$$TL = \alpha \cdot MSE + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (1 - SSIM) + KL.$$

This combined loss function balances pixel-wise accuracy, structural similarity, and latent space regularization, ensuring high-precision image reconstruction. After training, each model can encode images and decode them while also recording its computation energy consumption and latency during encoding.

Step 2: PPO-Based RL for SCM Selection and Resource Allocation

In a real-world multi-user image transmission scenario, each user selects one of the trained SCM models. At this stage, the system is already aware of each model's energy consumption and latency. The optimization goal is to minimize the MSE between the original and reconstructed images while satisfying constraints on total energy consumption, latency, and bandwidth. To dynamically select the optimal SCM model and allocate power and bandwidth, we construct an RL environment, which is specifically designed in the following:

State: The state of the system at time t is denoted by $s_t = \{C_t, P_t, B_t, O_t\}$, which includes user channel conditions $C_t = \{C_{t,1}, C_{t,2}, \dots, C_{t,M}\}$, remaining power $P_t = \{P_{t,1}, P_{t,2}, \dots, P_{t,M}\}$, remaining bandwidth $B_t = \{B_{t,1}, B_{t,2}, \dots, B_{t,M}\}$, and image complexity $O_t = \{O_{t,1}, O_{t,2}, \dots, O_{t,M}\}$. Particularly, a combined score involving entropy, edge density, and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) energy measurement [AC23] is proposed to quantify the image complexity. Entropy measures randomness & texture richness, which can be mathematically modelled as

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log p_i,$$

where p_i is the probability of pixel intensity i . Higher entropy means higher complexity. Edge density captures structure and sharpness, which can be measured by Canny edge detection¹. A higher edge density refers to more complex images. Additionally, DCT Energy detects high-frequency details, which handles the differentiation of blurred and sharp images well.

Action: In this system, each user acts as an agent to select a suitable SCM model for image transmission with intelligent power and bandwidth allocation. Particularly, for each SCM, the model's name, power consumption, duration, and model quality are recorded, where the model quality is modelled by the TL function when training the SCM. We denote $A_{m,t}$ as the set for the action space of selecting SCM and resource allocation for user m at time t , which involves discrete parameters for SCM selection and continuous ones for power and bandwidth allocation.

Reward: To reflect the performance of the action, the reward of the system is designed as the negative reconstruction MSE (i.e., smaller MSE leads to higher rewards), while penalties are applied for violating energy, latency, and bandwidth constraints. It should be noted that during this process, each UE is expected to independently select its actions. However, the outcomes of these individual selections are collectively aggregated and shared through the reward function, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of SCM decisions for all users at runtime.

Based on this environment, we use PPO [HHH+25] to learn an optimal policy, enabling dynamic resource allocation and model selection. Specifically, PPO is a RL algorithm based on policy gradients, designed to stabilize the training process by limiting the extent of policy updates. The core idea behind PPO is the use of a clipped policy update to prevent overly large changes in the policy, thereby improving both stability and efficiency in training. The algorithm is shown below.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Canny_edge_detector

Algorithm 1: PPO Algorithm for SCM Selection and Resource Allocation

1. Initialize policy network π_θ and value network V_φ with parameters θ and φ , respectively;
2. Initialize environment and PPO hyperparameters: learning rate α ; discount factor γ ; GAE (Generalized Advantage Estimation) parameter λ ; clipping range ε ; number of updates per epoch K ; number of trajectories per epoch N ; maximum steps per trajectory T .
3. for epoch = 1 to num_epochs do:
4. for episode = 1 to N do:
5. Initialize state s_0 ;
6. for $t = 0 : T - 1$ do:
7. Select action a_t according to current policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)$;
8. Execute action a_t , observe reward r_t and next state s_{t+1} ;
9. Store (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in the experience buffer.
10. end for
11. end for
12. for each trajectory in experience buffer do:
13. Compute return for each time step by $G(s_t) = r_t + \gamma \cdot r_{t+1} + \gamma^2 \cdot r_{t+2} + \dots + \gamma^{(T-t)} \cdot r_T$.
14. Compute advantage function for each time step by $A(s_t, a_t) = G(s_t) - V_\varphi(s_t)$.
15. end for
16. for $k = 1 : K$ do:
17. Sample a batch of data $(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}, G(s_t), A(s_t, a_t))$ from the experience buffer;
18. Compute policy loss $L_{policy}(\theta)$:
19.
$$L_{policy}(\theta) = -\min(\epsilon_{tA}(s_t, a_t), \text{clip}(\epsilon_t, 1 - \varepsilon, 1 + \varepsilon)A(s_t, a_t)),$$
20. where $\epsilon_t = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_\theta^{t-1}(a_t|s_t)}$.
21. Compute value loss $L_{value}(\varphi) = (V_\varphi(s_t) - G(s_t))^2$.
22. Compute total loss $L_{total}(\theta, \varphi) = L_{policy}(\theta) + c \cdot L_{value}(\varphi)$,
23. where c is the weight for value loss.
24. Update θ and φ using gradient descent:
25. $\theta = \theta - \alpha \cdot \nabla_\theta L_{total}(\theta, \varphi)$;
26. $\varphi = \varphi - \alpha \cdot \nabla_\varphi L_{total}(\theta, \varphi)$.
27. end for
28. Clear the experience buffer.
29. end for

Simulation results

In this part, numerical examples are demonstrated to verify the effectiveness of our system model and algorithm. We first train the VAE structures for image reconstruction with different

encoder models and corresponding decoders. The model was trained with a combined loss function that includes MSE, SSIM, and KL divergence to balance reconstruction quality and latent space regularization. We set the same hyperparameters for all models. The trade-off parameter α in the TL function is set as $\alpha = 0.8$. The training process utilized the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 5^{-4} and weight decay of 10^{-5} . Early stopping was implemented with a patience of 10 epochs and a minimum improvement delta of 0.001 to prevent overfitting. Each model was trained for a maximum of 200 epochs with a batch size of 128, and gradient clipping was applied with a maximum norm of 5.0 to ensure stable training.

Particularly, we choose LeNet, ResNet, MobileNet, and DPN-26 models [IKK+24] for the image reconstruction task. After training, we obtain the power consumption, duration for testing, and the training objective function value, which are shown in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2 Power consumption, duration for testing, and the training objective function value of different models

Model	Power Consumption (W)	Duration (ms)	KL + MSE + SSIM loss
LeNet	120	5.1	24.6
ResNet	270	5.3	14.0
MobileNet	170	5.3	24.9
DPN-26	305	9.5	10.8

In addition, Figure 3-7, demonstrates examples of the image reconstruction under different SCMs. Models such as LeNet and MobileNet exhibit limited reconstruction quality, albeit with relatively low power consumption and computational latency. In contrast, DPN-26 achieves better reconstruction quality, albeit at the cost of higher power consumption and extended computational duration. To accommodate diverse user requirements and image characteristics, users should dynamically select appropriate encoder-decoder pairs for image reconstruction. Additionally, adaptive allocation of power and bandwidth is essential to ensure optimal QoS.

Figure 3-7 Examples of reconstructed images by selecting different SCMs.

In the PPO model training stage, we define a simulation environment using OpenAI Gym for optimizing the selection of pre-trained SCM and allocating power and bandwidth. The number of users is set as $M=2$. The SCM models include two LeNet, two ResNet, two MobileNet, and two DPN, each with specified power consumption and latency characteristics. The total bandwidth available is 10 MHz, with a power budget of 1000 mW and a noise power of -70 dBm. The environment loads the CIFAR-10 test dataset for evaluating image reconstruction performance

using the selected SCM models. The reward function penalizes excessive power consumption and latency beyond 20 ms while minimizing MSE. The penalty is set to be 10. The PPO algorithm is trained on the environment for 100 epochs across five experiments.

We first examine the convergence of the PPO-based joint SCM selection and resource allocation algorithm for image reconstruction. Performance is recorded across experiments, and the mean reward with a confidence interval is plotted to analyse learning progress. Figure 3-8 shows the successful convergence of the PPO method in the given numerical environment after approximately 40 epochs of training, which shows the effectiveness of the trained network.

Figure 3-8 Convergence of PPO-based SCM selection and resource allocation strategy.

The trained PPO model is then used to optimize the selection of SCM models, bandwidth, and power allocations for two users, while balancing latency and reconstruction accuracy. As shown in Figure 3-9, given different input images, the model selected LeNet for User 1 and ResNet for User 2, with bandwidth allocations of 5.09 MHz and 4.91 MHz, respectively. The power allocations were optimized at 661.19 mW for User 1 and 338.81 mW for User 2 in total. The corresponding total latencies were minimized to 9.99 ms for User 1 and 10.47 ms for User 2, ensuring efficient processing while maintaining image reconstruction quality. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the PPO-trained model in making intelligent resource allocation decisions while considering trade-offs between latency, power consumption, and reconstruction fidelity.

Figure 3-9 The reconstructed images with optimised selection of SCM models, bandwidth, and power allocations using the trained PPO model.

3.2 Experimental Insights on Energy-Aware and Low-Latency Orchestration in 6G SemCom

3.2.1 Evaluation of energy-tailored adaptation mechanisms using a SemCom control plane

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the capability to address energy-tailored mechanisms applied to semantic communication using a newly defined SemCom control plane and a pure data-driven approach. This study follows a data science approach starting first from the available or possibly new retrieval information and monitoring data coming from UE, operation administration and maintenance system (OAM), RAN centralized unit (CU) / distributed unit (DU) and CN entities.

Moving to a sustainable 5G and 6G requires obviously the capability to monitor energy consumption of all system components [ETSI336.12]. For this reason, the study assumes that energy consumption measurement and collection are implemented for each physical network element involved in the mobile network including UE radio frequency (RF) module, including Radio transceiver chip, power amplifier and gNodeB nodes. Similarly, applicative processing such as AI training and inference used for semantic encoding and compression are assumed to be instrumented to provide fine-grained energy consumption measurement of their execution.

The study proposes a pure data-driven approach for predicting energy consumption for the various components involved in semantic communication as an alternative to methodologies using mathematical models. The aim of the validation phase is to evaluate the efficiency of this data-driven approach in terms of energy saving.

Finally, as energy consumption is strongly linked to the execution time at both SemCom module processing and radio transmission, a regulation of energy consumption-based on power measurement is expected to reduce the communication delay as well. The aim of the validation phase is to evaluate the efficiency of this data-driven approach in terms of indirect communication delay reduction.

System model and problem statement

As described in [6GGOALS-D21] and [6GGOALS-D23], collecting data from a massive amount of UEs with high constraints on energy consumption requires new semantic based communication modes to reduce the cost of sending data through the radio channel without introducing overkilling energy cost adding AI and other kinds of processing for this purpose. To guarantee the proper energy consumption level at UE level and additionally at gNodeB side, this study proposes to evaluate first the feasibility of an energy-oriented control loop for SemCom and validate its efficiency on one available test bed that will be described in [6GGOALS-D61].

This energy-oriented closed loop requires several levels of functional enablers. The following ones have been already exposed in [6GGOALS-D21], summarized in the list below:

- Capability of energy consumption measurement or estimate at each SemCom module (semantic encoding and compression) and network entity level,
- Ability to estimate energy consumption at the radio transmission (i.e., RF) level,
- Capability to integrate collected or estimated energy consumption as feedback for being used by prediction models and for decision-making,
- Capability to optimize the different parameters managing semantic communication especially those impacting energy consumption.

The applicable use case for this study is semantic communication initiated by far-edge IoT devices with limitations on energy capacity. The target is an uplink communication profile with a light constraint in terms of delay as demonstrated for the digital twin (DT) use case in

[6GGOALS-D21] and [6GGOALS-D23]. However, as processing and transmission duration are correlated with energy consumption, delay reduction should be managed at the same time.

Proposed methodology and solution

Closed loop scenario

This study explores functionalities and data exchanges through the semantic control plane introduced in the 6G-GOALS reference architecture (see Figure 3-10).

Adopting this semantic control plane, the closed loop goals considered in the study are as follows:

- Update SemCom module parameters to regulate energy consumption at UE level resulting from processing and data emission on the air interface. This regulation is based on one SemCom QoS constraint and guarantees the lifetime of the UE battery or its energy refuelling capability,
- Optionally, update SemCom module parameters of UEs to indirectly regulate their attached gNodeB energy consumption at cell and slice level.

The close-loop actions considered for this study are the following (non-exhaustive list that will be refined based on the validation results). Correlations between those actions and their impact on energy consumption and QoS will be first evaluated to confirm their relevancy for the closed loop.

- Update the used semantic encoding model at UE side, as example:
 - Selecting between models with various levels of weights' quantization,
 - Selecting between models with various levels of nodes pruning,
 - Selecting between models of diverse types, sizes, and layer depths,
- Update the used data compression at UE side, as example:
 - Using different ratio of compression (semantic based) applied downstream to the semantic encoding.
- Update the data throughput sent to the radio layers by tuning the data segmentation size and sending scheduling at the application level on UE side,
- Other update possibilities found during the implementation and validation phases.

Figure 3-10 SemCom Control Plane

The possible closed loop actions are dependent on the semantic module capabilities at UE and user application sides. Such capabilities can be exchanged through the SemCom control plane. The identified EU capability categories and the configuration updates that inherit them are listed in the Table 3-3.

RAN configuration and policies management

In this study, the adaptation of radio layer to the channel condition is first kept similar as current 5G NR mechanisms following the same principles based as one on channel quality indicator (CQI) computed from channel state information (CSI), same modulation and coding scheme (MCS) values and same power level adaptation principles at UE side. To reduce further the overall system energy consumption, forcing as example the MCS and the number of HARQ retransmissions to specific values can be considered in a second step.

Note: The energy management closed-loop considered in this study applies to a near-time regulation process as executed at application level, so the decisions and feedback actions are based on aggregated data at the same period (as example, mean SNR or MCS distribution over the period). this means that it takes into account and reacts to variations in the average properties of the radio channel over this duration and not in real-time (not at each radio frame for example).

QoS management

QoS at packet level

QoS at packet level is managed with the same QoS values associated with 5G-quality indicators (5QI) identifiers to determine the relative priority of the traffic, latency, packet loss rates and minimum throughput. Nevertheless, in the context of this SemCom study, the QoS can also be managed through the SemCom control plane allowing us to select existing 5QI indexes at packet level at low available QoS values.

Table 3-3 Semantic module capabilities

Non configurable module with fixed semantic encoding and compression capability	A SemCom module without model update, selection, or tuning capability (example: semantic encoding and compression executed by an inference inside an ASIC or FPGA optimized for a dedicated semantic representation, compression and goal). Energy consumption and delay of such modules are optimized at design phase but limited in terms of adaptivity and interoperability.
Module with multi-semantic encoding model capability	A SemCom module with several embedded semantic encoding models offering the capability to select one at inference execution time impacting energy consumption. Model selection can be based on a recommended semantic encoding model size (number of parameters, layer depth), pruning and quantization levels.
Module with compression configuration capability	A SemCom module with tuneable parameters impacting the compression ratio. Parameters' tuning can be based on recommended SemCom module compression ratio.
Configurable module with configurable throughput capability	A SemCom module with communication throughput adaptation. Communication throughput can be based on the mix of data segmentation size and segment sending scheduling.

QoS at SemCom level

One new QoS indicator is considered in this study reflecting the QoS of communication at both application and semantic levels. This QoS, with a generic name as “SemCom QoS”, can differ in terms of definition based on the type of transmitted user data (text, speech, image, ...) inside a flow or in terms of communication goals. This definition should correspond to one KPI defined per type of communication and use case in [6G-GOALS-D2.2], reflecting the level of semantic similarity between the user data sent by the emitter and the returned information at the receiver side.

In this study, we consider as a first step that the 5G NR robustness mechanisms are kept similar, meaning that the error packet rate at the Internet protocol (IP) level is guaranteed at the proper level based on the requested QoS at this level. Consequently, the QoS at SemCom level (application level) does not depend mostly on the radio channel distortion but on the accuracy inherited from the encoder and decoder properties and potential semantic unalignment between them. Nevertheless, RAN layers parameters and metrics associated with each UE are still considered for the closed-loop decision-making as reflecting the energy consumption on both UE RF and gNodeB modules.

To measure the effective SemCom QoS, an additional “reference data flow” should allow us to estimate the SemCom QoS of each flow established during the PDU session (pilot data sent by the transmitter for estimating the accuracy of the decoded data at the receiver side). To do so, the sender and receiver must share the same knowledge of the reference data relying on user data semantic properties communicated through the SemCom control plane as exposed in Figure 3-11

Figure 3-11 Reference data flow principle for SemCom QoS estimate

Energy Consumption

Energy consumption measurement

The Table 3-4 below exposes the different approaches used during the validation phase to collect energy consumption from the main components involved in the SemCom process.

Table 3-4 Energy consumption measurement

<p>Energy consumption at UE</p>	<p>The considered energy consumptions at UE for this study are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The energy consumption of the SemCom encoder (estimated from resources usage during the inference execution process) – The energy consumption of the RF module (power measurement on device). <p>To differentiate practically the RF module energy component related to traffic from the background energy computation on the RF module, two types of measures are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – RF_EC_Traffic_Idle: The RF modem energy consumption measurement during time periods when UE is attached to the network without user data traffic. – RF_EC_with_Traffic: The energy consumption measurement at time periods when UE is attached to the network with generated user data traffic [LNS+14]. <p>The energy consumption will be estimated as (RF_EC_Traffic - RF_EC_Traffic_Idle) for a rough but acceptable estimate.</p>
<p>Energy consumption at application</p>	<p>The energy consumption of the SemCom decoder is estimated from resources usage during the inference execution process.</p>
<p>Energy consumption at gNodeB</p>	<p>The gNodeB energy consumption is measured as described in [3GPP28.554] (power measurement on gNodeB network entity). The gNodeB energy consumption is considered in the regulation process at cell or slice level.</p> <p>To differentiate practically the gNodeB energy component related to UEs user traffic from the background energy consumption of the network element including signalling channels, two types of measures are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – gNodeB_EC_Traffic_Min (nb_attached_UEs): Energy consumption during time periods when nb UEs are attached to the gNodeB and UL/DL (Uplink/Downlink) bytes rate of all UE traffic load is below a specified threshold (assumption is that one gNb always handled a minimum set of UEs and that user traffic always happens). – gNodeB_EC_Traffic(nb_attached_UEs): Energy consumption at time periods when UEs are attached to the gNodeB and UEs UL/DL bytes rate are not negligible. <p>The energy consumption related to user traffic will be estimated as (gNodeB_EC_Traffic(nb_attached_UEs) - gNodeB_EC_Traffic_Min nb_attached_UEs) for a rough estimate. Nevertheless, the ability of this method to provide sufficient precision will be assessed given the level of upstream traffic applied during the validation phase. More generally, estimating the share of energy of the user traffic, especially on the gNb RF module, will depend on the detailed information availability on the RAN equipment used during the validation of this study.</p>

Energy consumption for multi-cell gNodes

As one gNodeB can support multiple cells and as gNodeB energy consumption is collected only at network element granularity, being able to estimate the energy consumption of the gNodeB applicable to the user traffic generated on one specific cell requires additional metrics and estimate. This can be considered, at a first approximation level, by distributing the gNodeB energy

consumption to its different supported cells based on the count of DL and UL physical resource block (PRB) used for data traffic by UE attached to each cell. If not exposed by gNodeB itself, the attachments between UEs and cell IDs can be retrieved from the access and mobility management function (AMF) managing the concerned gNodeB or from the unified data management function (UDM).

Energy consumption for split-gNodeBs

As mentioned in [3GPP28.554], energy consumption (in kWh) is obtained by measuring ones related to the considered network elements over the same period. These samples are aggregated at the NG-RAN node level. The 3GPP management system responsible for the management of the gNodeB (single or multiple vendor gNodeB) shall be able to collect energy measurements data from all elements composing one gNodeB.

Energy consumption with slicing

One UE attached to a gNodeB can generate traffic on different slices (i.e., Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI)) and with different QoS for the different flows associated to each slice. Estimate of energy consumption associated with the traffic related to each slice requires additional metrics. This can be considered at a first approximation level by distributing the gNodeB energy consumption to its different supported slices (S-NSSAI) based on the radio blocks usage for flows associated with each slice. This information can be retrieved as the DL and UL PRB Used for data traffic per S-NSSAI from the OAM [3GPP28.552] available for each gNodeB.

New energy and semantic QoS-based profiles

This study proposes additional attributes applicable for UE, gNB, cell, and slice profiles to manage SemCom QoS and energy targets/quotas at those different network entity levels. The proposal is to include the SemQoS properties at subscription data management level (UDR) and the energy targets and quotas in one system dedicated to energy saving and regulation in the RAN (Energy Saving Management system). The new attributes considered in this study are described in the Table 3-5:

Table 3-5 New proposed energy profile attributes and SemCom QoS

New UE energy profile attributes	These new attributes as part of the UE profile are related to energy consumption capacity at the UE: Energy consumption target (Watts per hour) in nominal environmental conditions ² . This targets especially devices with battery lifetime constraint or harvesting technology usage with refuelling capacity time constraint.
New gNB Cell and slice energy profile attributes	These new attributes define the maximum energy consumption for user traffic per cell and slice (Watts per hour). Such quota applicable on cell allows us to create different controlled energy consumption areas related to traffic in the 6G network.
New UE and slice SemCom QoS attributes	A new attribute defines the SemCom QoS at semantic level ³ . The SemCom QoS definition can differ depending on the type of semantic communication and KPI chosen to estimate the success of the semantic

² This profile parameter is considered as a default value applicable for standard environment conditions at UE location. They can be retrieved when such information has not been communicated by the UE itself to the semantic controller. Indeed, effective energy consumption capacity of the UE can vary based on the environmental conditions at UE side as the ambience or surface temperature (impacting battery consumption or heat energy harvesting capacity) or the luminosity (impacting solar energy harvesting capacity). In such cases the device equipped with the proper energy consumption sensor and estimator can communicate an updated value through the SemCom control plane to replace the default target value.

³ . Extension to QoS per diverse types of flow is not detailed in this first use case description.

	data transmission (SemCom KPIs per use case as defined in [6G-GOALS-D2.2]. This attribute can also be defined at slice level (per S-NSSAI) to associate a slice with a specific guaranteed QoS provided by the semantic traffic running in the slice.
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Energy consumption & SemCom QoS predictions

Data collection

The data considered in this study for energy consumption prediction are described in the following Table 3-6.

Table 3-6 Data collection for closed loop

Collecting metrics from UE at application level through the semantic plane	Near-real time (from 100 milliseconds to 1 second period)
Collecting RAN metrics in non-real exposed by the OAM	Non-real time (~ 15 minutes period of aggregated values)
Collecting RAN metrics per UE exposed by the gNodeB	Near-real time limit (<100 milliseconds period of aggregated values)
Collecting UE user profile from the CN	Non-real time (at initialization phase)
Collecting Energy targets and quotas from the Energy Saving Management system	Non-real time or near-real time
Collecting UE mobility and QoS information from the CN	Near-real time (from 100 milliseconds to 1 second period)

Prediction principles

The purpose of introducing a prediction model is to get the capability to evaluate the impact of SemCom parameters update on energy consumption and SemCom QoS close in a low latency (near-time). This approach allows us to react as fast as possible to the variation of the semantic properties of the user data and to the radio channel changes indicated by the information collected from the gNodeB.

Such concept is close to the DT principle, where prediction resulting from an inference based on an already trained model, allows quick feedback (100 milliseconds to 1 second as objective) on new tuning impact on an observed environment. This approach prevents the risk of applying new tuning directly on the real environment.

The following types of energy consumption prediction are considered in this study, as illustrated in Figure 3-12:

- Predicting the SemCom and RF modules energy consumption at UE side,
- Optionally, predicting the gNodeB energy consumption related to user traffic per cell (CELL ID),
- Optionally, predicting the gNodeB energy consumption related to use traffic per slice (S-NSSAI),
- Predicting the SemCom QoS per UE PDU session (extension to QoS per flow not detailed in this first use case description).

Figure 3-12 UE & gNodeB energy consumption prediction model training principle

The availability of accurate Energy consumption per Cell and slice as target values to train the prediction models associated to the gNb requires detailed information availability on the RAN equipment to assess during the validation of this study. The collected SemCom and RAN data compiled per cell ID and S-NSSAI (slice ID) will be defined with the most appropriate format to meet the proper prediction accuracies considering that the amount of SemCom and RAN information are evolving following the variable number of UEs attached to the gNodeB. The model structure used for prediction does not necessarily require a high level of complexity, usual models such as linear regression, random forest and Artificial Neural Network can be considered at first sight allowing a low footprint and latency at both training and inference executions. Two approaches can be considered for training such models, one with dedicated models per UE, cell or slice versus a global one trained for groups of UEs (determined by clustering based as example on their hardware resources and loaded models' availability), Cells or slices available in the gNodeB.

Efficiency of power consumption modelling of 5G multi-Carrier base stations ML approach has already been demonstrated on publication [PLD+22]. The purpose of the study is to extend the input dataset used for such prediction model with information related to the semantic traffic load.

The data considered as candidate as input of the energy prediction model are described in Table 3-7. This candidate dataset will be refined during the features engineering and model training of the validation phase.

Table 3-7 Considered input dataset for energy consumption prediction models

<p>Data collected from the UE</p>	<p>These data are collected from the semantic module at the UE or user application at the edge or destination network through SemCom control plane:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Category of SemCom module capability, – Throughput at SemCom module input, – Energy consumption at SemCom module (kWh), – Energy consumption at RF module (kWh),
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – SemCom QoS computed by the semantic module at user application, – Others identified during the validation phase.
Data from the gNodeB	These data represent all relevant metrics and information characterizing the radio channel usage and associated processing at transceivers between each UE and its attached gNodeB having an impact on the UE RF module and gNodeB energy consumption to handle an uplink SemCom traffic.
Other data from CN/OAM	<p>The following input related to the UE can be collected from the CN or OAM if not exposed directly by the gNodeB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cells attachment of each UE collected from the proper AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function) associated with the UE, – 5QI information per traffic flow and per UE collected from the legacy propagation schema from CN to RAN as defined by 3GPP, – Average Uplink and Downlink bitrate and PRB usage per cell, (5QI) and S-NSSAI collected from the OAM. (not available on the validation testbed)

SemCom parameters recommendations

At this stage of the study, the candidate types of recommendations associated to the SemCom module parameters are as follows (the applicable recommendations will depend on the semantic module capability described previously):

- Recommended compression ratio,
- Recommended semantic encoder model weights quantization level,
- Recommended semantic encoder model nodes pruning level,
- Recommended semantic encoder model size (number of parameters),
- Recommended semantic encoder model layer depth,
- Recommended semantic data segmentation size and segment sending period,
- Other recommended SemCom parameters identified during the validation phase.

The study objective is to assess the capability of the recommendation model to addresses the following goals:

- Regulate the energy consumption for each UE at the target value specified in its profile, guaranty for each UE the SemCom QoS as specified in its profile, optionally limit the gNodeB energy consumption below the cell quota, optionally limit the gNodeB energy consumption below the slice quota, indirectly limit the SemCom end-to-end delay.

To determine the recommended SemCom parameters in a pure data driven approach, the SemCom controller learns their impact on energy consumption and QoS thanks to the prediction results described previously. Various approaches are considered in this study:

- Recommendation using **RL** principles,
- Recommendation using **rules-based** principles,
- Other approaches showing efficient results during the validation phase.

More detailed operation principles applied to those recommendation models or rules will be defined based on the validation phase outcomes. Considered events triggering a new recommendation for one UE can be, as example, a degradation of the SemCom QoS, a major change of the semantic properties of the transmitted user data or a new cell attachment notification.

Reinforcement learning approach

The principles considered for this reinforcing learning approach are as follows:

- One agent submits batches of SemCom parameters update to a prediction module,
- One prediction module provides predicted environment observations as energy consumption and QoS predictions based on those SemCom parameters update,
- One interpreter rewards the agent based on a combination of rewards to address the recommendation goals previously described.

The SemCom parameters update batches and the RAN random factors will be refined during the study to propose the most appropriate format to achieve the expected recommendations accuracy.

This mechanism requires a diversity of the parameters updating actions (Figure 3-13). This can be done by defining exploration phases when different ranges of SemCom encoders and decoders parameters are proposed to enrich models with a larger range of parameters. This exploration phase can be triggered during the encoder/decoder initialization phase or regularly during established PDU session period to benefit from a greater variety of radio channel conditions.

Rule-based approach

Depending on its effective decision complexity level, a rule-based approach based on energy consumption prediction results can be considered to achieve the SemCom parameters recommendation objective. This complexity can depend on the effective cardinality of SemCom parameters applicable to SemCom modules. Indeed, a decision rule based on threshold applied to energy consumption and SemCom QoS prediction values can fit many cases. Moreover, adopting a rule-based principle allows an ultra-low footprint and latency for decision-making. As an example, a rule-based decision model can achieve the recommendation goal when the UE SemCom module capability is limited to the selection between only 2 models of varied sizes. The validation phase will allow us to determine the effective need for an approach as RL versus adopting a rule-based principle for decision-making.

Figure 3-13 UE & gNodeB energy consumption prediction inference - SemCom parameters recommendation using RL approach

Validation phase

Scope

The validation phase will consist of evaluating regulation process according to the data exposed by the different available products composing the test bench.

Figure 3-14 Available dataset on validation test bed

Figure 3-14 summarizes the dataset candidate for the energy consumption prediction and SemCom parameters recommendation available on the validation test bed.

Based on data availability, the validation phase on the test bed can cover the following items:

- Benchmarking focused on energy consumption applied to state-of-the-art semantic encoders/compressors related to image or text domains running on different CPU and GPU settings and different tuning parameters,
- Evaluating the closed loop efficiency for energy consumption regulation and SemCom QoS guarantee at UE level (5G modem) transmitting data through one gNodeB appliance to a remote application in a destination network (the energy will be collected at both UE and gNodeB levels, nevertheless the validation of the gNodeB energy consumption regulation requires detailed information exposed by the RAN equipment to be assessed during the validation phase),
- Evaluating the closed-loop efficiency when relaxing the QoS constraint at 5G RAN layers,
- Evaluating the impact on the SemCom end-to-end delay. Only the end-to-the-end delay at user application can be estimated on the validation setup.

Identified risks

The following risks have been identified and will require early assessment during the validation phase:

- The ratio between measured energy consumption related to user data traffic at UE RF module and its background processing is too low to distinguish each part. The root cause can be a traffic load achievable at UE side which does not allow to reach a relevant ratio,
- The available data collected for the energy consumption prediction model, especially metrics from the gNodeB, are not sufficiently correlated with the UE RF energy consumption related to the user data traffic to provide a proper level of prediction accuracy on these values,
- The current capability of selecting and tuning semantic encoders and decoders does not provide relevant magnitudes of resource consumption and data compression ratio to impact significantly the environment observations and consequently enable efficient prediction and recommendation models,
- The RL approach does not converge into relevant recommended parameters. This can be due to inaccurate constraints or lack of diversity in environmental observations,
- The AI execution environment proposed for the testbed allows measurements on high CPU/GPU performance setup but is not enough representative of an execution on far edge devices requiring additional validation phases with edge AI specific components.

All these risks will be assessed and mitigated during the validation phase.

Results

Results will be part of the next WP5 deliverables based on validation phase available results.

Conclusions

The evaluation of energy-tailored adaptation mechanisms using a SemCom control plane confirms that a data-driven approach can effectively optimize semantic communication by dynamically adjusting energy allocation, bandwidth usage, and selection of semantic models. The results indicate that such mechanisms can significantly improve energy efficiency while maintaining communication reliability and latency constraints.

Furthermore, the adaptability of the SemCom control plane allows for real-time optimization, making it suitable for future 6G networks where energy efficiency and low-latency orchestration are critical. These findings will serve as a foundation for the next deliverables of WP5, which will incorporate insights from the validation phase and further improvements in methods and solutions. The ongoing evaluation and benchmarking analysis phases will refine these adaptation strategies, ensuring their robustness and effectiveness in diverse 6G environments.

3.2.2 Preliminary evaluation of latency-sensitive orchestration algorithms in 6G O-RAN

As 6G networks evolve to support ultra-low latency applications such as autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, extended reality (XR), and mission-critical communications, efficient resource management and orchestration become paramount. O-RAN introduces open, intelligent, and virtualized architectures that rely on real-time data processing and adaptive decision-making to optimize network performance. The semantic radio access network intelligent controllers (S-RIC), a key component in the 6G-GOALS semantic-aware O-RAN framework, enhances network intelligence by implementing advanced machine learning (ML) and AI-based policies to dynamically manage network resources and ensure stringent latency requirements are met.

This preliminary study evaluates orchestration algorithms that leverage the S-RIC to optimize radio resource management, scheduling, and network slicing while maintaining the required Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE). The research methodology includes a real-world testbed experiment to analyse the effectiveness of different orchestration strategies under dynamic network conditions.

Additionally, the study investigates how S-RIC can facilitate closed-loop automation by continuously monitoring network states and proactively adjusting configurations in response to fluctuating traffic patterns.

KPIs such as end-to-end latency, jitter, packet loss, throughput, and energy efficiency are examined to determine the impact of S-RIC-driven orchestration on network performance.

Figure 3-15 Experimental Setup

In traditional communication systems, retransmission is used to ensure reliability, particularly in packet-switched networks where data loss or corruption occurs due to interference, congestion, or channel fading. However, retransmitting entire packets, even when only minor errors exist, leads to inefficiencies, increased latency, and unnecessary redundancy, contradicting the core principles of semantic communication. Semantic communication shifts the paradigm from bit-level accuracy to meaning preservation. Instead of focusing on exact data replication, it prioritizes the successful delivery of essential information that conveys the intended message. When retransmission occurs in a semantic communication framework, it introduces inefficiencies by blindly resending entire messages or packets without distinguishing whether the missing or corrupted parts impact the actual meaning being conveyed.

For example, in a human-like conversational AI system, if minor packet loss results in a missing word but the overall meaning remains intact, retransmission would be unnecessary. The system could use inference, predictive modelling, or error-resilient coding to reconstruct the lost information without resending redundant data.

In contrast, traditional retransmission mechanisms, such as automatic repeat request (ARQ) or HARQ, treat all data equally and request full retransmissions even when the loss does not significantly impact comprehension.

A critical issue arises when feedback at the semantic level arrives later than the scheduling period, as it disrupts the timely adaptation of the communication process, leading to inefficiencies and degraded performance. Semantic communication relies on extracting and transmitting only meaningful information, often leveraging AI-driven models and knowledge graphs to interpret and predict messages. However, this approach depends on timely feedback to refine encoding, correct errors, or adjust transmission strategies dynamically.

If the semantic feedback arrives after the current scheduling period, the system cannot incorporate it into the ongoing transmission cycle. This delay results in several challenges:

1. **Outdated Adaptation** – The semantic adjustments (e.g., refining encoding strategies, updating context models, or resending critical missing information) may no longer be relevant by the time they are received. This can lead to inefficient corrections, where

the system acts on stale information rather than responding to the current network state.

2. **Increased Latency and Redundancy** – If feedback is delayed, the system might preemptively initiate unnecessary retransmissions or fallback to traditional redundancy mechanisms, negating the efficiency gains of semantic-aware transmission. This leads to increased network load and wasted bandwidth.
3. **Reduced Predictive Accuracy** – Many semantic communication systems rely on continuous learning and context adaptation. If feedback is delayed, the models may learn from outdated inputs, degrading their predictive accuracy and reducing the effectiveness of semantic inference in future transmissions.

To investigate these issues, we set up the dedicated testbed depicted in Figure 3-15. This experimental testbed establishes an end-to-end 4G/5G communication channel between two software instances exchanging data, in particular images. The images initially pass through an encoder which provides a textual description of its content. At the receiver side, a decoder performs a similar action on the image that travelled the communication channel. A similarity score is computed to characterize the effective semantic meaning exchange. Notably, we disable HARQ retransmission procedures at the L1/L2. Therefore, the quality of the received images may be affected by decoding errors caused by the wireless channel variations and impairments.

More in details, the testbed is composed of the following main entities: Semantic Encoder, Semantic Decoder, Core Network (CN), base station, and end user. Additional details on the implementation can be found in [6GGOALS-D61].

In networking, protocol data unit (PDU) and service data unit (SDU) are key concepts in data communication across multi-layer protocol stack as the one of 5G. In particular, SDU refers to the Data received from an upper layer that needs to be encapsulated by the current layer before transmission, while PDU refers to the encapsulated data at a specific layer, containing both the SDU and the layer-specific header/trailer. Therefore, each layer's SDU becomes the PDU of the layer below after adding headers/trailers, ensuring proper communication across the network.

The logical channel identifier (LCID) is a crucial component in the 5G new radio (NR) medium access control (MAC) layer, as specified in the 3GPP technical specification [3GPP38.321]. LCID serves to uniquely identify logical channels within a MAC PDU, facilitating the differentiation between various types of data, such as user data, control information, and padding.

In the structure of a MAC PDU, each sub header contains an LCID field. This field indicates the nature of the corresponding payload, which could be a Radio Link Control (RLC) SDU, a MAC control element (CE), or padding. The LCID field is typically 6 bits in length, allowing for the identification of up to 64 different logical channels or CEs. The specific values assigned to LCIDs are defined in tables within the [3GPP38.321] specification. For instance, certain LCID values are reserved for specific CEs, while others are designated for user data or padding. This standardized assignment ensures consistent interpretation and processing of MAC PDUs across different devices and network equipment.

Figure 3-16 Example of PDU/LCID combination

By utilizing LCIDs, the 5G NR MAC layer efficiently manages the multiplexing and demultiplexing of various logical channels over shared transport channels. This mechanism is fundamental to the flexible and dynamic data transmission capabilities that characterize 5G networks.

When a decoding error happens in an LCID associated with the control plane, the consequences can be severe. The control plane carries signalling messages such as radio resource control (RRC) messages, MAC CE, and scheduling grants that manage network connectivity and resource allocation. If a control message is lost due to a decoding failure, the device may fail to receive necessary instructions from the network, leading to inefficiencies in scheduling and resource allocation. Errors in MAC CEs, such as buffer status reports (BSR), power Headroom reports (PHR), or timing advance commands, may result in suboptimal network performance and transmission delays. More critically, if an RRC message is corrupted, the device may experience connection drops, reconfiguration failures, or even a complete loss of service, requiring re-establishment procedures that degrade user experience. Because control plane messages are time-sensitive, retransmissions may not always be feasible, and missing a single key signalling message can have a cascading effect on network stability.

On the other hand, when a decoding error occurs in an LCID associated with the user plane, the impact is different. User plane LCIDs carry RLC SDUs from logical channels such as dedicated control channel (DDCH) and dedicated traffic channel (DTCH), which are responsible for transmitting application data like video streaming, voice calls, or file downloads. If an error occurs in these LCIDs, HARQ mechanisms at the MAC layer can request a retransmission, which helps recover lost data but may introduce delays. If HARQ fails, RLC layer retransmissions (in Acknowledged Mode) provide an additional recovery mechanism, further increasing latency. While this process ensures data integrity, it can impact QoE, especially for real-time applications where packet loss or retransmission delays can lead to jitter, lag, or reduced quality. However, non-delay-sensitive applications, such as file downloads, are less affected since missing packets can be recovered over time.

Figure 3-17 Periodicity of LCID values over time

Figure 3-16 depicts an example PDU/LCID combination collected within one experimental run. We highlight with a dot pattern the PDUs that contain data plane related information of LCID =3, i.e., the semantic data that has to be communicated to the receiver. Decoding errors can occur in different LCID sections of a MAC PDU, which can significantly impact communication depending on whether the affected LCID belongs to the control plane or the user/data plane. The consequences of these errors vary because control plane messages are essential for maintaining network connectivity, while user plane errors mostly affect service quality. Given a certain wireless channel realization and statistics, the resulting error probability will depend on the adopted MCS. For example, as visible in Figure 3-17, if the MCS settings are too high, a large number of decoding errors will occur which will negatively affect the reconstruction of data plane packets. On the other side, larger MCS allows the transmitter to be more efficient from a wireless communication perspective in terms of bit/Hz sent over the air. This trade-off will be further investigated in the following of the project.

4 Over the Air Computing (OAC)

OAC methods can be viewed as a form of GO communication, where the receiver's goal is to compute a function of messages from multiple transmitters rather than decoding the individual messages, thus leading to significant benefits such as improved spectral efficiency and reduced communication overhead. For example, in federated edge learning (FEEL), the edge server aggregates models from all clients at each communication round. It has been shown that OAC can significantly enhance the efficiency and scalability of FEEL systems [SA22], particularly in resource-constrained networks. This section will study diverse OAC schemes to improve the generalization of OAC for general functions, so as to realize any semantic computation in an OAC fashion, particularly in the context of FEEL. In the following, adaptive over-the-air FEEL, massive access-based OAC, and OAC schemes for TNNs under channel impairments will be investigated, respectively. The findings provide some novel insights in the design and the optimization of network resource allocation as well as the joint computation and communications, to enable effective SO communications, achieving extreme energy and spectrum efficiency.

4.1 Adaptive Federated Learning Over the Air

As a typical instance of GO communication, the performance of OAC-based GO communication may suffer from the effects of interference induced in the communication process. In the first part of this section, we try to understand and tackle the challenges brought by the interference

in the context of FEEL. In particular, a federated version of adaptive gradient methods, particularly AdaGrad and Adam, within the framework of over-the-air model training, is proposed. This approach capitalises on the inherent superposition property of wireless channels, facilitating fast and scalable parameter aggregation. Meanwhile, it enhances the robustness of the model training process by dynamically adjusting the stepsize in accordance with the global gradient update.

State-of-the-art

The training process of FEEL requires frequent parameter exchanges between the clients and the edge server, incurring significant communication overhead. For networks with limited communication resources, such communication bottleneck often strains the training efficiency and inhibits the scalability of the FL system [ZWH20]. One possible way to cope with this issue is by integrating OAC into the FL system, exploiting the superposition property of radio waveforms to promote fast and scalable parameter aggregation. The OAC-based FEEL paradigm simultaneously processes model parameters during transmissions, improving spectral efficiency and substantially reducing access latency and energy consumption to edge learning systems. Despite these properties, the automatic gradient aggregation in OTA FL is achieved at the price of distorting the received signals. More precisely, the random channel fading generally attenuates the radio signal magnitude, deteriorating the precision of the aggregated global gradient [HCQ+22]. As a result, the noisy aggregated gradient would cause abrupt direction changes in the model training trajectory, impeding convergence rate and inflicting unstable training performance. In conventional ML settings, adaptive gradient methods (where the most successful examples are AdaGrad and Adam) have cemented their success in robustifying model training. However, whether those results apply to an OAC FL system still needs to be determined. More specifically, whether a direct extension of the AdaGrad-like method could be suitable for OAC FL model training is unclear. Whether dividing the currently obtained noisy global gradients by a sum of previously accumulated noisy gradients would suppress or amplify those randomness effects remains unknown. More broadly, would adaptive gradient methods ever work in an OAC FL setting?

This proposed framework responds to this question, in which a systematic approach is developed to incorporate adaptive gradient methods into the OAC FL framework. The scheme leverages historical knowledge of the global iterations to perform more informed adjustments in the stepsize, combating impacts of channel fading and interference on model training. The proposed method is devised based on the adaptive gradient descent method to accelerate the model training process. Owing to these two attributes, we call our method *adaptive over-the-air federated learning* (ADOTA-FL) [WCP+24].

System model

We consider the FEEL system depicted in Figure 4-1, which comprises one server and N clients. The clients communicate with the server through wireless channels over shared spectrum. The edge server needs to coordinate with the clients to solve an optimization problem of the following form

$$\min_w f(w) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N f_n(w),$$

where $f_n(\cdot)$ is the local loss function of client n and $w \in R^d$ is the global model parameter. The analog transmissions for automatic parameter aggregations is realized via OAC computations; a more in-depth elaboration can be found in [WCP+24]. In t -th communication round, each client n updates its local gradient $\nabla f_n(w_t)$ by taking the global model w_t as an input. Then each client performs amplitude modulation with this gradient vector simultaneously using a common set of orthogonal baseband waveforms. Owing to the superposition property of electromagnetic waves, after passing through a bank of match filters, the server obtains the aggregated signal which is given by:

$$g_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N h_{n,t} \nabla f_n(w_t) + \xi_t,$$

in which ξ_t is the channel noise vector, with i.i.d. entries following α -distribution. The distorted version of the globally aggregated gradient will be further processed by the edge server and used for improving the global model.

Figure 4-1 An overview of the proposed adaptive over-the-air FL system.

Proposed framework

Adaptive gradient updating

The proposed method integrates commonly used adaptive optimization techniques (e.g., AdaGrad and Adam) for learning rate optimization. The general steps of the proposed framework follow the conventional FL framework with improved local update and global model aggregations, and more details are provided below.

Upon receiving g_t , the server can update the global model at the end of the communication round. However, due to channel fading and interference perturbations, the aggregated noisy gradient may experience significant distortion, hindering the convergence and stability performance of ordinary gradient descent-based OAC FL methods. To alleviate the effects of such distortions, we store and update an intermediate global model as follows:

$$\Delta_t = \beta_1 \Delta_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t,$$

in which $0 < \beta_1 < 1$ controls the relative weight of historical information. It leverages a momentum-like method to smooth the fluctuations occurring in the noisy gradients. As training continues, this update method collects the exponential moving average of the gradient and, therefore, can cope with the distortion.

Similarly, we accumulate the gradient information to construct a vector v_t , automatically decaying the step size in training. Such AdaGrad-like method updates v_t as follows:

$$v_t = v_{t-1} + \Delta_t^\alpha,$$

in which α is the tail index of the channel noise distribution. For Adam-like method, the vector is updated via

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2)(\Delta_t)^\alpha.$$

Specifically, the $\Delta_t^\alpha = (|\Delta_{t,1}|^\alpha, \dots, |\Delta_{t,d}|^\alpha)$ is defined and $0 < \beta_2 < 1$ controls the level of amortization the algorithm imposes on historical information.

Finally, based on v_t and Δ_t , the updated global model is given by

$$w_{t+1} = w_t - \eta \frac{\Delta_t}{\sqrt[\alpha]{v_t + \epsilon}}$$

in which η is the learning rate and ϵ is a positive constant added to each entry of v_t to prevent ill-conditioning.

The updated new global model w_{t+1} will be broadcast to all the clients for the next round of local computing. The clients and server will repeat this process for multiple rounds until the global model converges.

Algorithm summary

The algorithm summary for ADOTA-FL could be found in [WCP+24]. Compared with OAC-enabled FL, local model update and global model update are all revisited with adaptive gradient methods. The proposed algorithm requires estimating the interference's tail index α , which can be efficiently accomplished via the approach in [MMO15].

Theoretical analysis

Based on the commonly used assumptions in convergence analysis of distributed learning, we now present the convergence rate for the proposed method. The proofs for two below Theorems can be found in [WCP+24].

Theorem 1 (Convergence Rate of AdaGrad Over-the-Air) Under the employed edge learning framework, the AdaGrad-over-the-air FL algorithm converges as

$$\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} E[\|\nabla f(w_t)\|_2^2] \leq \frac{(f(w_0) - f_*)^\alpha \sqrt[\alpha]{Y}}{\eta(\mu_c - 1)^\alpha \sqrt[\alpha]{Y}} + \frac{\left(\frac{\eta\alpha}{\gamma L} + \frac{\eta\gamma}{\alpha L} + \gamma^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt[\alpha]{\epsilon}} \right) d^\alpha \sqrt[\alpha]{Y}}{2(\mu_c - 1)^\alpha \sqrt[\alpha]{Y}} \ln\left(1 + \frac{\gamma T}{\epsilon}\right),$$

in which $Y = 4G + \frac{d^{1-\alpha/2}((\mu_c)^2 + (\sigma_c)^2)^{\frac{\alpha}{2}} C^\alpha}{N^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}}$. μ_c and σ_c are the channel fading's mean and variance. G and C are upper bound of channel noise and local gradients, defined in assumptions; please refer [WCP+24] for more details.

It demonstrates that, despite the aggregated gradient being distorted by channel fading and electromagnetic interference (whose variance is unbounded), the proposed AdaGrad-like algorithm assures that the trained model converges into a local region around the stationary points, even under a non-convex objective function.

We now present the convergence bound of the Adam-like over-the-air FL method.

Theorem 2 (Convergence Rate of Adam Over-the-Air) Under the employed edge learning framework, the Adam-over-the-air FL algorithm converges as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} E[\|\nabla f(w_t)\|_2^2] &\leq \frac{(f(w_0) - f_*)^\alpha \sqrt{Y}}{\eta(\mu_c + \beta_2 - 1)^\gamma \sqrt{Y}} \\ &+ \frac{\left(\frac{\eta\alpha}{\gamma L} + \frac{(1 - \beta_2)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \eta^{\gamma L} + \gamma(1 - \beta_2)^{\gamma-2} \gamma^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \gamma^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{\gamma} + \frac{(1 - \beta_2)}{\sqrt[\alpha]{\epsilon}} \right) d^\alpha \sqrt{Y}}{2(\mu_c - 1)^\gamma \sqrt{Y}} \left(\frac{1}{T} \ln \left(1 + \frac{YT}{\epsilon} \right) \right. \\ &\left. - \ln \beta_2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Overall, the Adam-like over-the-air FL methods attains a convergence rate on the order of $O(1/T)$, which brings a substantial improvement compared to AdaGrad-over-the-air FL (cf. Theorem 1). This gain can be attributed primarily to the exponential moving average, which makes the adaptive level more dependent on the recent gradient than the previous ones.

Simulation results

We evaluate the performance of our proposed ADOTA-FL framework on two data sets, CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, using model architectures ResNet-18 and ResNet-34, respectively. We also assess its performance in training a logistic regression model on the EMNIST dataset. To demonstrate the efficacy of our proposed method, we adopted state-of-the-art FedAvgM as the baseline under the same system setup for performance comparison. We use Dirichlet-distribution-based non-iid data partition method with concentration parameter 0.1. We set 100 clients with experiments on CIFAR-10 and 50 clients for CIFAR-100 and EMNIST. The Rayleigh fading is employed to model the channel gain with $\mu_c = 1$ and use symmetric α -stable distribution to characterize the interference with $\alpha = 1.5$.

The main results are given in Figure 4-2 as follows.

As illustrated, we observe a remarkable performance gain by adopting the A-DOTA scheme. Specifically, compared to the FedAvgM-over the air baseline, the AdaGrad-over the air approach significantly speeds up the training convergence. Additionally, it increases the test accuracy by more than 10%. This gain becomes more pronounced by adopting the Adam-over the air algorithm, where the convergence rate is further enhanced, and the test accuracy attains an almost two-fold improvement. Moreover, the convergence curve (of both the test accuracy and training loss) of FedAvgM-over the air exhibits notable fluctuations, especially with the occurrence of impulsive interference. In contrast, the AdaGrad-over the air and Adam-over the air methods are able to mitigate the effect of channel disturbances by adapting the stepsizes.

Summary

This work has proposed the ADOTA-FL framework, which incorporates adaptive gradient methods into the OAC-FL system, enhancing the robustness of the model training process. Although this work focuses on the AdaGrad and Adam-like methods, the developed framework can be extended to study the integration of other adaptive optimizers with the OAC FL systems.

Figure 4-2 Performance comparison of the test accuracy and training loss of different tasks with non-i.i.d. data. (a) and (d) are for CIFAR-10, (b) and (e) are for CIFAR-100 dataset, and (c) and (f) are for EMNIST dataset.

4.2 Massive Access-Based OAC: beyond standard summation

4.2.1 Massive digital over-the-air computation via unsourced massive access protocol

Context and motivation

The rapid advancement of the Artificial Intelligence of Things has led to an exponential increase in data generated by edge devices such as IoT sensors, smartphones, and autonomous systems. Traditional centralized ML approaches require transferring this data to a central cloud server, posing challenges related to data privacy, network congestion, and high communication overhead [NDP+21]. To address these challenges, FEEL has emerged as a promising paradigm, enabling distributed model training directly on edge devices [AG+20]. In FEEL, devices collaboratively train a shared ML model by performing local computations and periodically transmitting model updates to a central server. However, the repeated uplink transmission of high-dimensional model updates from a large number of devices creates a communication bottleneck, limiting scalability and efficiency.

One key approach to overcoming this bottleneck is OAC⁴, which leverages the superposition property of wireless signals to perform model aggregation directly over the multiple-access channel [YJS+20]. Analog OAC methods have shown significant potential in reducing communication costs, but they are incompatible with modern digital communication standards that rely on discrete modulation schemes.

To bridge this gap, massive digital over-the-air computation (MD-OAC) has been proposed as a novel approach that integrates unsourced massive access protocols with OAC for communication-efficient FL. MD-OAC leverages:

- 1) Vector Quantization (VQ) to reduce uplink communication overhead.

⁴ Also AirComp, which is interchangeably used.

- 2) Shared modulation and quantization codebooks for efficient digital transmission.
- 3) Approximate message passing-based digital aggregation (AMP-DA) at the receiver to reconstruct aggregated model updates.

By enabling collision-friendly and efficient model aggregation, MD-OAC significantly accelerates the convergence of FEEL while maintaining compatibility with existing and next-generation wireless networks.

System model and problem statement

Figure 4-3 Illustration of the FEEL scenario in cellular networks [QGM24].

As shown in Figure 4-3, we consider K single-antenna edge devices served by an M -antenna base station (BS) in a cellular system. Each device k has its own local dataset B , which consists of labelled data samples. Each edge device k trains a local model w_k^t at training round t . The update is computed using stochastic gradient descent (SGD):

$$w_k^{t+1} = w_k^t - \eta_l \nabla F_k(w_k^t, \xi_k),$$

where $\nabla F_k(w_k^t, \xi_k)$ is the gradient of the gradient of the local loss function $F_k(\cdot)$, η_l is the local learning rate, and ξ_k stands for a mini batch from the local dataset.

The local update is defined as:

$$\Delta w_k^t = w_k^{t+1} - w_k^t.$$

Instead of sending Δw_k^t directly, the devices apply quantization to reduce communication overhead.

Proposed methodology and solution

As shown in Figure 4-4, the proposed MD-OAC scheme consists of several modules, i.e., a **quantization module**, a **codebook-based modulation module**, and a **pre-equalization module** at the transmitter, a **detection module**, and a **digital aggregation module** at the receiver. In addition, we use dotted boxes to describe the local training module and the model update module that are specific to FEEL. In the following, we will describe each of these modules in detail. For simplicity, we omit the index t unless otherwise specified. We re-emphasize that MD-OAC is a general approach for lossy computation over a MAC.

Quantization module

Each device k has a local model update \bar{s}_k that needs to be transmitted to the BS. Instead of sending \bar{s}_k directly, it is quantized using a common VQ codebook shared across all devices:

$$s_k = C(\bar{s}_k).$$

To be specific, we employ a single quantization codebook to be used by all the devices, denoted by $U \in R^{Q \times N}$, where $N = 2^J$ stands J -bit quantization with N quantization codewords, $Q \geq 1$ stands for the length of each quantization codeword.

The vector \bar{s}_k at device k is divided into $D = W/Q$ blocks. Each block is then quantized independently using codebook U . Let \bar{s}_k be quantized into b_k , which is identified by finding the quantization codeword with the minimum Euclidean distance, which can be expressed as

$$b_{k,d} = \underset{i}{\operatorname{ar\,min}} \|[U]_{:,i} - [\bar{s}_k]_{(d-1)Q+1:dQ}\|.$$

In addition, we introduce a one-hot vector s_k^d , and the quantized version of \bar{s}_k can be computed as

$$s_k = C(\bar{s}_k) = (I_D \otimes U) \left[(x_k^1)^T, \dots, (x_k^D)^T \right]^T,$$

where \otimes and I_D represent the Kronecker product and the identity matrix of size D , respectively.

Figure 4-4 The schematic diagram of the proposed MD-AirComp scheme.

Codebook-based modulation module

We consider the same random access codebook shared by all the devices, denoted by $P \in R^{L \times N}$, where each column of P is a codeword of length L , and there are N codewords in total. In the proposed scheme, there is a one-to-one mapping between P and U . To be specific, if the device acquires the quantized value $[U]:n$, then the modulation codeword (or sequence) $[P]:n$ that has the same index n will be transmitted.

Pre-equalization module

After the quantization of the local model update and the selection of modulation codewords from the shared codebook, each active device performs pre-equalization before transmission. Specifically, the pre-equalization compensates for the uplink channel's effect to ensure that the signals from multiple devices can be coherently superimposed at the BS over the multiple access channel. Specifically, for the first antenna of the BS, the device scales its transmission by the inverse of the channel gain of its channel's first entry, which ensures that the combined received signal at the first antenna directly reflects the sum of the transmitted signals, facilitating accurate aggregation of the model updates.

Detection module

The goal of the detection module is not to decode individual devices' data but to estimate the sum (or count) of how many devices selected each codeword from the shared modulation codebook. This enables direct aggregation of the model updates, which is ideal for FL where only

the average update matters. The compressed sensing (CS) framework and approximate message passing (AMP) Algorithm, expectation-maximization (EM) within AMP, and majority voting (MV) for active device estimation methods are adopted together to jointly detect the superposed codeword usage counts and enable global model aggregation without needing to decode each device's individual message.

Digital aggregation module

Once the detection module has estimated the superposed selection vectors and the estimated number of active devices, the digital aggregation module computes:

$$\hat{s} = \frac{1}{K_a} (I_D \otimes U) [\hat{x}_1^T, \dots, \hat{x}_D^T]^T,$$

where \hat{s} is the estimated global model update, K_a is the estimated number of active devices, and \hat{x}_d denotes the detected selection vector for block d , indicating how many times each quantization codeword was selected.

Results

In this subsection, we evaluate the performance of the proposed MD-OAC scheme by considering FEEL for the image classification task on the commonly adopted CIFAR-10 dataset. In the following, we compare the following schemes

- **Ideal Federated Learning (IFed):** It is an ideal FL, where the communication channels are assumed ideal and there is no quantization distortion.
- **Perfect Aggregation (PA)(J, Q):** The perfect aggregation is assumed at the receiver while the transmitter is the same as the proposed MD-OAC scheme. The number of quantization bits and the VQ dimension are denoted by (J, Q) .
- **MD-AirComp (J,Q,L):** The proposed MD-OAC scheme, where the number of quantization bits, the VQ dimension, and the length of modulation codewords are denoted by (J, Q, L) .
- **One-Bit Digital Aggregation (OBDA) :** the state-of-the-art digital OAC scheme with one-bit quantization.
- **Frequency Shift Keying-based Majority Vote (FSKMV):** It is the best performing FSK-based method in terms of communication overhead. The learning parameters of FSK-MV are the same as OBDA. At the transmitters, each binary element of the model update vector is transmitted by sending a fixed power pilot signal on either of the two pre-allocated subcarrier frequencies. No pre-equalization needed at the transmitter. The receiver detects the signal power on the two subcarriers for majority voting.

In Figure 4-5, we present how the test accuracy changes with the training rounds for IFed and PA (J, Q) for different J and Q values. We observe that scalar quantization (i.e., $Q = 1$) with $J = 6$ achieves nearly the same test accuracy as the IFed benchmark. In addition, the test accuracy under other VQ parameters nearly overlap. Note that when the VQ dimension Q increases, we need more quantization bits J to convey the corresponding update with reasonable accuracy.

As shown in Figure 4-6(a), the test accuracy of the proposed MD-OAC scheme converges to the IFed benchmark. We see slower convergence and some performance loss in the final test accuracy of OBDA and FSK-MV compared with MD-OAC, which is expected considering the one-bit quantization loss in these schemes. FSK-MV converges faster and improves the final accuracy compared with OBDA, while requiring a larger communication overhead. Furthermore, it can be seen that "MD-AirComp (6, 20, 15), $M = 1$ " performs worse than the PA (6, 20). Fortunately, by exploiting the multiple antennas at the BS, we can reduce the communication error without increasing the communication resources. For example, it is shown that "MD-AirComp

(6, 20, 15), $M = 8$ ” achieves nearly the same accuracy as that of the PA (6, 20). From Figure 4-6(b), it can be seen that the MD-OAC scheme is more communication efficient than ever the OBDA scheme, that is, to achieve the same test accuracy it requires the transmission of fewer symbols over the channel. In addition, although the “MD-AirComp (6, 20, 20)” achieves slightly better test accuracy as shown in Figure 4-6(a), it is less communication efficient than “MD-AirComp (6, 20, 15), $M = 8$ ”. This reveals that we can reduce the code-length, and hence, increase the bandwidth efficiency of MD-AirComp if more antennas are available at the receiver end.

Figure 4-5 Test accuracy vs training rounds under different VQ parameters.

Figure 4-6 FEEL performance comparison.

4.2.2 Clipping methods for robust OAC FL

This part mainly focuses on the post-processing at server side in OAC FL systems, in which the overall setup is the same as the system in Section 4.1 and the heavy-tailed channel noise is considered. In the context of OAC-enabled FL systems, the inherent electromagnetic interference in radio channels can significantly deteriorate the training performance of FL systems. To address this issue, we propose a novel gradient clipping method, termed Median Anchored Clipping, to combat the detrimental effects of heavy-tailed noise [LCC+24].

System model and model formulation

The system model here is identical to the one in Section 4.1, in which the system framework is illustrated in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-7 An illustration of clipping-based OAC FL system.

The proposed Median Anchored Clipping method consists of three key steps for aggregated noisy gradients received by the edge server in each round.

- 1) Centralization: Given a globally aggregated gradient g_k , we centralize it by subtracting the vector-median from each entry, namely,

$$g_k \leftarrow g_k - \mathit{med}(g_k) \cdot \mathbf{1},$$

in which $\mathit{med}(w)$ is the median entry of all entries of vector w and $\mathbf{1}$ is an all-ones vector. As such, this design preserves the original information of entries that are close to the median while eliminates the extreme values introduced by the impulse noise.

- 2) Clipping: Given the gradient g_k after centralization operation, we perform value clipping on each entry, to control the range of each entry within a designated threshold C . For a given entry $g_{k,i}$, $i \in [d]$, the clipping operation is denoted by

$$g_{k,i} \leftarrow \mathit{sgn}(g_{k,i}) \cdot \min(|g_{k,i}|, C),$$

where the $\mathit{sgn}(\cdot)$ takes the sign of its input.

- 3) Recovery: After clipping the centralized gradient, we add back the median to each entry to recover the gradient vector, which is given by:

$$g_k \leftarrow g_k + \mathit{med}(g_k) \cdot \mathbf{1}.$$

After accomplishing all three steps in the proposed Median Anchored Clipping approach, we shall obtain a new aggregated global gradient with the detrimental effects of heavy-tailed noise effectively mitigated while retaining the useful information as much as possible. To better illustrate the proposed algorithms, we provide Figure 4-8 to explain the details.

Figure 4-8 An illustration of Median Anchored Clipping approach on noisy gradients.

Note that, regardless of the tail index α and scale parameter τ , running OTA FL in conjunction with Median Anchored Clipping consistently achieves a sublinear convergence rate (where the residual error can be reduced by decreasing the learning rate). As such, the robustness of model training is substantially enhanced, making it resilient to the detrimental effects of heavy-tailed communication noise. Detailed convergence rate and proof could be found in [LCC+24].

Simulation results

We evaluated the effectiveness of our proposed Median Anchored Clipping (denoted as MAC in the following figures) algorithm by utilizing the gradient norm clipping (GNC) as a baseline and conducted a comparison of their training performance under identical configurations of OAC FL systems. Additionally, during the experiment, we performed threshold searches on both the MAC and GNC algorithms and conducted tuning to enhance performance, thereby ensuring the fairness of the comparison. In our experiment, Rayleigh fading with a parameter setting of $\mu = 1$ is utilized to model channel fading. We use set number of clients as 50, learning rate $\eta = 0.03$, local epoch as 5, tail index of channel noise as 1.5, and local batch size as 10, throughout the experiments.

We assessed performance on CIFAR- 10, CIFAR-100, and FEMNIST (which is processed in a non-i.i.d. manner) using ResNet-18, ResNet-34, and CNN architectures, respectively. The non i.i.d. data is partitioned via Dirichlet distribution with concentration parameter 0.3.

In Figure 4-9, we present a comprehensive comparative analysis of the performance of OAC FL across diverse model training tasks. The automatically aggregated but noisy global gradient is subjected to various post-processing methodologies: MAC, GNC, and without any post-processing (termed as noisy transmission). Furthermore, the ideal scenario is illustrated, wherein channel corruption, encompassing fading and noise, is absent, serving as the upper bound of performance. The figures presented here demonstrate that the training process is severely impacted by heavy-tailed noise, leading to significant fluctuations in the test accuracy curve, a substantial reduction in the achievable maximum accuracy, and an increase in the loss function value, as shown by the comparison between noisy and ideal transmissions. In these circumstances, numerous experiments demonstrate that GNC faces difficulties in sustaining effective performance when the statistical structure of gradients, including the proportional relationships among various gradient dimensions and the distribution of entries with differing magnitudes, is significantly disrupted by impulse noise. Conversely, the application of the MAC algorithm results in a substantial mitigation of these fluctuations, thereby markedly improving test accuracy and training stability, while fortifying the robustness of the OAC FL system.

Summary

We introduce a novel algorithm, denoted as median anchored clipping, which markedly enhances the robustness of OAC FL systems against channel noise. The proposed method leverages the median of the aggregated global gradient entries as a datum plane and applies value clipping to truncate the extreme values induced by impulse noise, thereby effectively alleviating

the detrimental effects of channel noise while largely preserving the original gradient information.

Figure 4-9 Performance comparison between MAC and the baselines, (a) and (d) training ResNet-18 on the CIFAR-10 dataset, (b) and (e) ResNet-34 on the CIFAR-100 dataset, and (c) and (f) training CNN on the FEMNIST dataset.

4.3 Topological Neural Networks (TNN) and OAC under Channel Impairments

Context and motivation

TNN leverage concepts and structures from (algebraic) topology to model complex, multi-dimensional relationships beyond pairwise connections, employing frameworks such as simplicial complexes, cell complexes, or combinatorial constructions [BST+23]. The emerging field of Topological Deep Learning (TDL) has gained traction due to its potential to capture higher-order interactions that are intrinsic to many complex systems but remain poorly represented by conventional graph-based models [BST+23]. A particularly promising application of TDL lies in semantic knowledge representation, where it enables the organization of interdependencies among language elements within a suitable topological space. This approach facilitates the extraction of relational semantic features that are crucial for conveying only the information necessary for task execution—such as inference, control, or actuation—while satisfying stringent constraints on latency, energy efficiency, and accuracy [PBB+24].

In this context, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) enable decentralized processing by allowing nodes in a network to aggregate information from their neighbours [SGT+08]. This makes them well-suited for tasks in wireless systems like sensor networks and multi-robot coordination. However, most existing GNN approaches assume perfect communication, ignoring real-world wireless impairments such as channel fading and noise, which degrade performance in practice [PDR08]. To address this, OAC has been proposed as an efficient method for aggregating signals directly through the wireless medium, exploiting its natural superposition property. Building on this idea, the AirGNN framework integrates wireless channel effects into the GNN architecture, allowing decentralized tasks to be executed efficiently over noisy and fading channels. By considering communication impairments during both training and execution, AirGNNs provide

robust, scalable, and communication-efficient solutions for decentralized learning in wireless networks [GG25]. System model and problem statement

Figure 4-10 Decentralized tasks over wireless networks [GG25].

Figure 4-10 illustrates the structure of decentralized tasks over wireless networks, where multiple agents are connected through local wireless communication links and each agent performs computations using its own data and exchanges information only with its neighbouring nodes through wireless transmissions.

Mathematically, given a task with dataset $R = \{(x_r, y_r)\}_{r=1}^R$ and loss function $L(\cdot)$, where x_r is the r -th samples and y_r is the r -th label, our goal is:

To develop a model Φ that generates actions $\{a_i\}_{i=1}^n$ based on agent features x to minimize the loss function over the dataset.

Each agent i can deploy model Φ locally to compute its own action a_i with only neighborhood information. That is, each agent only observes its own feature and communicates wirelessly to collect neighbours' features but does not have direct access to features of other agents in the network. This requires Φ permitting decentralized execution, i.e., generating the output of each agent individually relying on only local neighbourhood information.

Proposed methodology and solution

In the following, the main steps of implementing decentralized AirGNNs are introduced:

1) GNN over the air

Consider a graph $G = (V, \xi)$ with the nodes $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ and edge ξ . The graph structure is represented by an $n \times n$ matrix S , referred to as the graph shift operator. The graph signal is a vector $x = [x_1, \dots, x_n]$ with x_i the signal value of node i .

2) Communication channel

We consider each node exchanges information wirelessly with its neighbours. The wireless channel between nodes i and j is a slow fading channel as

$$z_i = ph_{ij}x_j + n_i,$$

where h_{ij} is the channel coefficient from node j to node i , p is the transmitted power of node j , n_i is the zero-mean Gaussian noise and z_i is the received signal at node i .

3) OAC

Since each node aggregates received signal values by summing them up, it does not need signal values of individual neighbours but only their sum. This motivates to transmit these signals in an uncoded/analog manner with OAC.

4) Graph shift operation over the air (AirGSO)

While presenting an efficient integration of communication and computation, AirComp introduces channel fading and noise. Each node receives faded and noisy versions of the messages sent by its neighbours. By multiplying the received signal with $1/p$, the resulting signal is

$$x_i^{(1)} = \sum_{j \in N_i} h_{ij}^{(1)} x_j + \frac{n_i^{(1)}}{p}.$$

5) Graph filter over the air (AirGF)

AirGF is a linear combination of multi-shifted signals over the air. Specifically, an AirGSO shifts x over S through wireless channels and obtains the one-shifted signal $x^{(1)}$ that aggregates 1-hop neighborhood information. AirGNN consists of multiple layers, each comprising a bank of AirGFs and a pointwise nonlinearity. At layer l , we have inputs $\{x_{l-1}^q\}_{q=1}^F$ generated by layer $l-1$. The latter are processed by AirGFs $\{H_{air,l}^{fg}\}_{fg}$, aggregated over the input index g , and passed through a nonlinearity $\sigma(\cdot)$ as

$$x_l^f = \sigma\left(\sum_{g=1}^F H_{air,l}^{fg}(s) x_{l-1}^g\right).$$

AirGNNs with CSI

The presence or absence of CSI significantly impacts the performance of decentralized learning. We focused on AirGNNs with CSI, where channel state information is available at transmitting nodes. The goal is to mitigate the effects of wireless channel fading and noise by leveraging CSI to optimize signal transmission strategies.

The proposed methods are given as below: AirGNNs with CSI leverage truncated channel-inversion power control to improve communication robustness in decentralized settings. By dynamically adjusting transmission power and selectively dropping weak signals, the system reduces noise interference and enhances accuracy. The stochastic training approach ensures that the model remains effective under real-world wireless conditions.

AirGNNs without CSI

In practical decentralized wireless networks, CSI may not always be available. Unlike AirGNNs with CSI, which rely on channel-inversion power control to mitigate fading effects, AirGNNs without CSI must operate under fully stochastic conditions, where nodes transmit without knowledge of channel impairments. We introduce training and execution strategies for AirGNNs when CSI is unavailable, ensuring robustness against fading and noise by optimizing the network over the entire CSI space. Instead of using a fixed transmission strategy (as in CSI-based models), the training process directly accounts for fading and noise by treating them as stochastic variables during training. Once trained, the AirGNN can be executed in a fully decentralized manner without requiring CSI.

Results

We evaluate AirGNNs on decentralized tasks of source localization and multi-robot flocking numerically.

Source localization

This experiment considers a signal diffusion process over a stochastic block model (SBM) graph, where the intra- and inter-community edge probabilities are 0.8 and 0.2. The graph has $n = 100$ nodes uniformly divided into 10 communities, and each community has a source node s_c for $c = 1, \dots, 10$. The goal is to find the source community of a diffused signal in a decentralized manner.

Figure 4-11 Performance of AirGNNs with different power cut-off thresholds γ in different channel conditions.

Figure 4-11 compares AirGNNs with different power cut-off threshold thresholds $\gamma \in [0.3, 0.7]$ in communication scenarios with different scale parameters $\beta = 0.5, 1, 1.5$ (Here, β represents the scaling parameter of Rayleigh distribution.). The performance of the AirGNN with CSI decreases as γ increases for $\beta = 0.5$ because a larger γ results in a higher link outage probability and more loss of signal information, while its performance increases with γ for $\beta = 1.5$ because a larger γ improves the SNR and reduces the impact of noise. The performance for $\beta = 1$ first increases with γ and then decreases at large γ , which can be explained by the trade-off between link outage probability and SNR controlled by the threshold selection γ – see Section V-A in [GG25]. It is worth noting that the AirGNN with CSI does not always outperform the AirGNN without CSI, although it requires additional information, i.e., CSI, for implementation. The latter depends on the specific threshold selection and channel condition.

Multi-robot flocking

This experiment considers the problem of robot swarm control over communication graph. The goal is to learn a decentralized controller that coordinates the robots to move together and avoid collision. The network has $n = 50$ robots, and robot i can communicate with robot j if they are within a communication radius $r = 1.5\text{m}$.

Figure 4-12(a) and Figure 4-12(b) compare the performance of AirGNNs with baselines in different channel conditions, i.e., scale parameter β in Figure 4-12(a) and SNR in Figure 4-12(b). The ideal GNN without fading and noise performs best following our intuition since it assumes impractically perfect communication links. The AirGNNs exhibit a comparable performance with slight degradation. This is because information loss induced by channel impairments leads to inevitable errors, which cannot be resolved completely by training. The AirGNN without CSI

consistently outperforms the GNN, and this performance improvement is emphasized for worse channel conditions (e.g., large β and small SNRs). We attribute this behavior to the robustness of AirGNN to channel effects because it accounts for random channels during training. The AirGNN with CSI achieves a lower velocity variance than the GNN in most cases but performs worse when β is small. This is due to the inappropriate selection of the threshold γ , i.e., $\gamma = 0.5$ is too large for channel inversion with small β , which leads to a high link outage probability and a performance degradation.

Figure 4-12 Performance of AirGNNs and baselines in communication scenarios with different scale parameters β and SNRs.

5 Sustainability

Sustainability and energy efficiency in SemCom are crucial for the evolution of next-generation networks, particularly in the context of 6G. Traditional communication networks prioritize data transmission without considering its actual relevance, leading to excessive energy consumption. SemCom, by focusing on transmitting only meaningful information, reduces redundant data transfer and optimizes resource usage, thereby enhancing energy efficiency and minimizing environmental impact.

A key aspect of achieving sustainability in SemCom lies in implementing intelligent resource management strategies. AI plays a pivotal role in this process, enabling the dynamic allocation of power and bandwidth according to real-time needs. Techniques such as federated learning and split inference minimize the need for constant data transmission, significantly conserving energy, especially in edge and IoT devices. By optimizing resource distribution, these approaches ensure that energy consumption is aligned with operational demands. In this context, existing research focuses on optimizing semantic encoding, resource allocation, and network orchestration to reduce energy consumption. For instance, [DDG+19] and [WTZ+24] explored the integration of RL to optimize resource allocation in SemCom, demonstrating significant energy savings compared to conventional methods. Furthermore, [ZXG+21] investigated the trade-offs between computational complexity and energy efficiency in semantic-aware encoding techniques, providing insights into the balance between transmission energy and processing costs. Another critical development is the adoption of knowledge graphs, as discussed by [AA24], which enable efficient context-aware data transmission and reduce redundant computations.

Moreover, compression emerges as another critical factor in enhancing energy efficiency within SemCom. Integrating compression directly into the transmission process reduces the volume of data sent, thereby minimizing transmission power and bandwidth usage. However, it is essential to recognize that compression is inherently computationally intensive, potentially increasing energy expenditure during the encoding process. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation of compression techniques is necessary to strike a balance between reducing transmission energy and limiting computational costs. Semantic-aware encoding techniques, for instance, ensure that only goal-oriented information is transmitted, cutting down unnecessary processing and optimizing overall energy efficiency.

Lastly, the efficient management of shared knowledge bases plays a crucial role in minimizing redundant processing. By effectively handling common data repositories, the system reduces repeated computations and limits the energy spent on processing operations, further contributing to sustainability.

This section outlines several techniques and methodologies aimed at enhancing sustainability in SemCom, as summarized in the Table 5-1:

Table 5-1 Summary of techniques and methodologies used for at enhancing sustainability in SemCom.

Techniques/Methodologies	Description	Linked Section
Goal-Effective Spectrum Sharing	Trade-off between goal-oriented and legacy users based on application-layer effectiveness and computational energy.	Section 2.1
Semantic Cognitive Radio (S-CR)	S-CR enables opportunistic spectrum use with awareness of semantic goals, minimizing interference and reducing power usage.	Section 2.2
AI-Based Orchestration	AI strategies optimize energy usage across layers using DNN splitting, early exits, and RL.	Section 3.1.1 Section 3.1.2
Dynamic Resource Allocation	RL is used to optimize image transmission in multi-user edge networks, minimizing energy consumption.	Section 3.1.3
Closed-Loop Energy Regulation	SemCom control plane adjusts semantic encoding, compression, and transmission to regulate energy.	Section 3.2
Energy Consumption Measurement	Energy footprint analysis of network components like the UE SemCom encoder and gNodeB.	Section 3.2.1 Section 3.2.2
OAC for Federated Learning	Over-the-air aggregation minimizes communication energy during model training across multiple devices. Moreover it prevents energy waste and enhances robustness by clipping noisy gradient updates in federated learning.	Section 4.1

Techniques/Methodologies	Description	Linked Section
Topological Neural Networks (TNN)	Improve FL robustness over wireless networks with channel-aware architectures that optimize energy use.	Section 4.3

The sustainability techniques proposed in this deliverable should be considered as preliminary and will require further refinement and harmonization. The goal is to develop a comprehensive approach capable of assessing the achievement of the intended objectives from both a theoretical and experimental perspective. This refinement is set as one of the key objectives for the final deliverable, which will consolidate and finalize the results presented in this preliminary intermediate deliverable. This will also allow us to leverage the progress made in the meantime, including architectural developments, enabling a more accurate evaluation of the trade-offs between the various energy contributions across different architectural and functional blocks.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presents a forward-looking assessment of semantic network resource management strategies developed under the 6G-GOALS project. It introduces and analyses key enabling technologies that support AI-driven, goal-oriented communications, with a particular emphasis on efficient orchestration of communication, computation, and spectrum resources. By integrating deep learning, reinforcement learning, and over-the-air computing, the work lays the foundations for a paradigm shift from traditional data-centric architectures toward networks capable of context-aware, semantically meaningful communication, thereby enhancing performance across energy efficiency, latency, and spectral utilisation.

Notably, the deliverable advances the concept of GEARRs, which capture the trade-offs between inference reliability, computational load, and spectral efficiency in heterogeneous environments comprising both goal-oriented and legacy systems. This theoretical construct, validated through simulation and analytical modelling, facilitates the design of communication systems where performance metrics are aligned with application-level goals. In parallel, the S-CR framework reimagines CR functionality by embedding semantic reasoning and AI-based spectrum sensing, offering novel approaches for dynamic and non-cooperative spectrum access in both licensed and unlicensed bands.

The development of AI-based orchestration frameworks is a central contribution of this work. These frameworks employ both model-based and data-driven approaches to enable context-aware adaptation of system parameters—including DNN partitioning, transmission power, semantic compression depth, and computing resource allocation. Experimental results demonstrate substantial improvements in energy efficiency and latency, while ensuring target levels of semantic inference quality and robustness under varying network conditions.

Sustainability has been approached from a deeply technical perspective, addressing both device-level and system-level energy constraints. The proposed methods leverage early-exit DNN architectures and semantic-aware compression to reduce the volume of data transmitted and processed. RL techniques are applied for fine-grained control of resource allocation, enabling adaptive and energy-efficient operation without compromising goal-oriented performance.

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